

**HEAD-MODIFIER STRUCTURES IN
THE ÌGBÒ LANGUAGE**

BY

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DEDICATION

TO
ALL MY TEACHERS
AND
MENTORS

CERTIFICATION

I certify that this thesis was carried out by Stephen Madu Anurudu in the Department of Linguistics and African Languages, University of Ibadan, under my supervision

Supervisor

Emeritus Professor Ayo Bamgbose

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LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

A	-	Adjective
A/D	-	Autonomous profile determinant
A-P	-	Articulatory-perceptual Interface
AGR	-	Agreement
AGRIO	-	Indirect Object Agreement
AGRO	-	Object Agreement
AGRP	-	Agreement Phrase
AP	-	Adjective or Adverb Phrase
Appl	-	Applicative
ASPP	-	Aspect Phrase
BVC	-	Bound Verb Complement
C	-	Characteriser
C-I	-	Conceptual-Intentional Interface
CGN	-	Cognate nominal
CH _L	-	Computational System of Human Language
Comp	-	Complementizer
Conj	-	Conjunction
ConjP	-	Conjunction Phrase
CP	-	Complementizer Phrase
D	-	Determinative/Dependent Component
DBP	-	Derivation by Phase
DP	-	Determiner Phrase
ECM	-	External Case Marking
EM	-	External Merge

EPP	-	Extended Projection Principle
ESI	-	Enlightened Self Interest
EST	-	Extended Standard Theory
FC	-	Functional Categories
FPPH	-	Full Functional Projection Hypothesis
FL	-	Faculty of Language
GB	-	Government and Binding
GenP	-	Genitive Phrase
GER	-	Gerund
HH	-	High and High tones
HS	-	High and Downstepped tones
IC	-	Inherent Complement
IM	-	Internal Merge
imp	-	impersonal pronoun
INFL	-	Inflection
Inf	-	Inflection
INFP	-	Infinitival Phrase
IP	-	Inflectional Phrase
LCA	-	Linear Correspondence Axiom
LCS	-	Lexical Conceptual Structure
L2	-	Second Language
LF	-	Logical Form
LI	-	Lexical Item
LL	-	Low and Low tones
ModP	-	Modifier Phrase

MP	-	Minimalist Program
MT	-	Mother tongue
N	-	Noun
NP	-	Negation Phrase
NP	-	Noun Phrase
NTC	-	No Tampering Condition
O	-	Object
O ₁	-	Object 1
O ₂	-	Object 2
PF	-	Phonetic Form
PN	-	Personal Name
PP	-	Prepositional Phrase
P&P	-	Principles and Parameters
R-Expressions	-	Referring Expressions
RHR	-	Right Hand Head Rule
RTAH	-	Relative Theta Assignment Hypothesis
SC	-	Small Clause
SO	-	Syntactic Object
ST	-	Standard Theory
Subject	-	Subject
TConj	-	Conjunction Transformation
TP	-	Tense Phrase
UTAH	-	Uniform Theta Assignment Hypothesis
V	-	Verb
VP	-	Verb Phrase

ABSTRACT

Previous works on the noun head-modifier structures in Igbo, over the years, analysed them to have two configurations – the prevalent head-modifier structure and the exceptional modifier-head structure. Problems arise as to which configuration is in place when a given expression can have both the head-modifier and the modifier-head structures, in which case, the two possibilities can be used interchangeably. This is the case with shifted modifiers. The study, therefore, investigated the issue of shifted modifier placements in the Igbo language by finding the reason for the shift and gave theory-based explanations for them.

Ten purposively selected Informants were interviewed and library-based data collection method was also employed. Two informants each were taken from the Orlu dialect, Owerri dialect, Anioma dialect, Enugu and Ngwa dialects representing different geographical zones of Igboland. Analysis of the data involved presentation of well-formed and ill-formed expressions, comparing and analysing them based on the principles and operations of the Minimalist Program which is used as the theoretical model. The feature-theoretic approach of this framework is used since it provides a more economy-based method of data interpretation and analysis.

Three head-modifier configurations are identified in the Igbo language and also the extremity feature is responsible for modifier shift in the language. The three configuration possibilities for the head-modifier distributions in the language are: one, the head could be the initial element of the phrase, which is the norm; two, it could be preceded by a modifier obligatorily. This is the case with nouns such as *ezigbo*, which cannot be postmodified. Such nouns must have originated from a post-head position but had to shift to a pre-head position due to extremity feature. Three, the modifier could optionally precede the head. This is the case with nouns in the class of *omaricha*, which can post-modify or pre-modify their heads. The last two options are essentially possible with nouns expressing extremities in terms of intensification, and gradability. Other findings include the exceptive modifiers such as *naānj* and *sooso* which have

several combinatorial possibilities and the activities of the verb *ima* which triggers the displacement of its nominal modifiers. Thus, modifier-shift operation is feature-driven because of the need to show extremity. This then leads to a conclusion that there is, in fact, an intra-lexical movement comparable to that obtained in syntactic movement. Intra-lexical is taken here to mean within a noun phrase, which we call a phrase-internal operation.

In Igbo, head-modifier and modifier-head structures are possible with certain nominal modifiers. The two views on head-modifier relations can indeed be harmonized. The findings will provide further logic and analytical framework for advancement in computational linguistics.

Keywords: Head-modifier, Movement, Noun, Igbo language, Modifier-shift.

Word count: 435.

CHAPTER ONE

BACKGROUND TO THE STUDY

1.0 INTRODUCTION

Language, according to generativists, is a mental phenomenon and its proper knowledge and understanding would give insight into how the human mind works. Supporting this assertion, Chomsky (1972:103) states:

There are a number of questions which might lead one to take a study of language. Personally, I am primarily intrigued by the possibility of learning something, from the study of language, which will bring to light inherent properties of the human mind (Chomsky, 1972)

The study of languages serves then the purposes of understanding language itself and how the human mind works. As to what aspects of human language study would yield the expected results, Chomsky (in the same paper) gives three related theories of language study which yield the expected results. They are: the theory of language structure, the theory of language acquisition, and the theory of language use. The first concerns the structural properties of natural languages; the second deals with how children acquire their native languages; and the third explore how linguistic and non-linguistic knowledge interact in speech comprehension and production. Of the three, the theory of language structure has received much more attention and study than the other two in generative grammar, considering the volume of studies that have been done over the last three decades.

In the terminology of Chomsky (1986b:19-56), a study of language is a study of the cognitive system internalized within the human brain/mind, and as such, the ultimate goal is to characterize the nature of the internalized linguistic system

for I-language) which enables humans to speak and understand their native language. Chomsky (1986b: 36) puts it this way:

Linguistics, as a discipline, is characterized by attention to certain kinds of evidence that are for the moment, readily accessible and informative; largely, the judgments of the native speakers. Each such judgment is in fact, the result of an experiment, one that is poorly designed but rich in the evidence it provides. In practice, we tend to operate on the assumption or pretense, that these informant judgments give us 'direct evidence' as to the structure of the I-language (internalized language, i.e., language which the speaker has internalized), but of course, this is only a tentative and inexact working hypothesis and any skilled practitioner has at his or her disposal an armoury of techniques to help compensate for the errors introduced. In general, informant judgments do not reflect the structure of the language directly; judgments of acceptability, for example, may fail to provide direct evidence as to grammatical status because of the intrusion of numerous other factors. The same is true of other judgments concerning form and meaning. (Chomsky, 1986b: 36)

The summary of all that has been said above is that native speakers have the innate ability to make intuitive judgments about the acceptability of certain sentences. However, there is a need for a proper theoretical explication of the workings of the human language, hence the need for an adequate theory of language. To underscore that point, Chomsky in an earlier work says:

We may make intuitive judgment that some linguistic expression is odd or deviant. But we cannot in general know, *pretheoretically*, whether this deviance is a matter of syntax, semantics, pragmatics, belief, memory limitations, style, etc., or even whether these are appropriate categories for the interpretation of the judgment in question. It is an obvious and uncontroversial fact that informant judgments and other data do not fall neatly into clear categories: syntactic, semantic, etc. (Chomsky 1977)
(Emphasis; mine.)

The knowledge of grammaticality possessed by a native speaker about his language cannot be measured without a theoretical paradigm, hence the need for a well-articulated and well-structured linguistic theory that meets the adequacy criteria of description and explanation.

The main concern of every descriptive linguist is to devise grammars of particular languages. The theoretical linguist, on the other hand, has to devise grammatical theories that take into consideration not only the descriptive features of languages but also explanations for certain phenomena that occur in languages, not only for a particular language but for all languages. As Radford (1997) rightly observes, such a theory, that adequately describes and explains language features, must be universal, explanatory, restrictive, minimally complex, and learnable. A universality criterion is an offshoot of the I-language or the innateness hypothesis from which the idea of a universal grammar stems.

Whatever evidence we do have seems to me to support the view that the ability to acquire and use language is a specific human capacity, that there are very deep and restrictive principles that determine the nature of human language and are rooted in the specific character of the human mind. (Chomsky, 1972:102).

The deep and restrictive principles that determine the nature of languages are called principles of Universal Grammar while the variable aspects of those principles are called parameters of Universal Grammar. The question as to why languages differ in their structure in spite of the universality of language is answered by the Principles and Parameters approach of Chomsky (1981). Languages have the same overriding principles that guide the formation of sentences but the actual configuration is parameterized. Binary parameter implies that learnability criterion imposes only two choices for a child learning any language. One of the principles of UG that is not controvertible in any language is the *structure dependence principle*. This principle states that syntactic operations are done within a given structural domain (Radford, 1997a: 13-15, 25).

The grammatical parameters of UG include: the *wh*-parameter, null subject parameter, and head parameter. The main concern in this study is with the *head parameter*. UG parameter specifies that a language is either head-first or head-last. A head-first language puts the head first and then its modifiers follow, while a head-last language has the opposite configuration. If a more adequate (descriptive and explanatory) theory would capture all the features of language, then seeming parameter violations should be accounted for. This study seeks then to do just that.

1.1 LITERATURE REVIEW

Since no meaningful study can be done in isolation, a review of studies on Igbo grammar in general and the noun phrase in particular is briefly discussed below.

One of the first efforts at capturing a grammar of Igbo in a general frame is Ward (1936). The aim of Ward's grammar, a pioneer work, is

"to set out the results of research into the tones and tonal behaviors of Ibo, and to present these results in such a way as to introduce the learner to the difficulties of the language gradually, as far as this is possible. It may be considered as a kind of handbook covering the initial stages of grammar and tones..." (Introduction p. ix).

Ida Ward gives a good account of the simple sentences, subordinate clauses, and infinitives in Igbo although she could not make specific statements as to why certain aspects of the grammar behave the way they do. This is possibly because insights into certain aspects of syntax were not well understood then as they are now.

Another description of Igbo grammar which has turned out to be a reference point for all scholars of the Igbo language is Green and Igwe's (1963), *A*

no denying the fact that they translate the English adjectives good, bad and new. But there are thousands and one other nouns which also translate English adjectives, and which never occur alone, though they can be in first or second position in a nominal construction. Given this situation, and the absence of any diagnostic syntactic or morphological criteria for adjectives in Igbo, we suggest a neutral term, nominal, for these items and all well-established nouns of the language. It is the task of grammarians to determine which of these nominals can function alone as NP, which require another nominal $[N_1 N_2]_{NP}$, those with fixed structural position, and those without fixed structural position. (Nwachukwu 1975:202).

The lexical items in question in the excerpt above include: *oma*, good/fine, *ocha*, white, *ojo*, bad/ugly, *ajo*, bad/wicked, and *ukwu*, big, *ezigbo*, original etc. Scholars such as Emenanjo (1978), Oluikpe (1979) and Uwalaka (1997) have, however, distinguished between true adjectives and nominal adjectives with definite distinguishing criteria. So it is to his credit that he raises the issue of fixed and free nominal modifiers which we will discuss in this study. His treatment of the various aspects of the Igbo noun clause is exhaustive.

Some recent studies on Igbo grammar include Emenanjo (1975, 1978), Oluikpe (1978, 1979), Anagbogu (1990), Mbah (1999), and Uba-mgbemena (2006) among others. A review of these studies is given below since they relate to the topic of the present study. In a descriptive manner, Emenanjo (1978) gives a principled schematization of the Igbo NP structure as in (1).

(1) (A) + N + (A + P + Nm + Q + D + Q + RC)

Where () = Optionality

A = Adjective

N = Noun

P = Pronominal modifier

Nm = Numeral

Q = Quantifier

Descriptive Grammar of Igbo. This study is considered the most comprehensive and detailed grammatical description of the Igbo language in existence. Its proposal of a tone-marking system that leaves the high tones (H) and marks the low tones (L) and the downstepped tones is still one of the most accepted conventions till date. However, because of the copious description of many aspects of the Igbo grammar, there is no way it can exhaustively treat all the aspects of the language.

Using the transformational model of grammatical description, Patricia Carrell's *A Transformational Grammar of Igbo* (1970) is a theory-based analysis of the Igbo language. It treats the Igbo grammar in a larger frame excluding a detailed syntactic analysis. Nevertheless it sets the stage for more theory-based studies on Igbo language.

Another significant contribution to the study of Igbo grammar is the work of Nwachukwu (1975). This work gives a detailed theory-based analysis of the Igbo noun phrase syntax. Using a Transformational Grammar (TG) approach, it looks at the forms of noun complementation in the language from a sentential perspective. Succinctly put, Nwachukwu's work deals with the noun clause. It treats the aspects of noun-modifier word order, rejecting the category, adjective, as a way of having a uniform account for the noun phrases. He says that lexical items such as: *oma*, *ajo/ojoo*, *ocha*, *ukwu*, *ojii*, *phuu* and other noun-qualifying words should be recognized as nominals and not adjectives, contrary to the view of most Igbo language scholars among whom are Green and Igwe (1963), Carrel (1970). On page 202 of his study, (footnotes), he says:

Lexical items such as these are classified as adjectives by scholars of the Igbo language, notably Green and Igwe (1963) and Igwe (1974). There is

- D = Demonstrative
 RC = Relative Clause Emenanjo (1978:80)

The schema in (1) implies that an adjective may (not) post- and/or pre-modify the Igbo noun, contrary to the Universal Grammar head parameter selection which requires that heads of phrases either precede their modifiers or follow their modifiers. Other modifiers come after the noun. Also he observes that certain qualificative nouns (nouns that function as adjectives) do not have fixed position in the noun phrase just as Nwachukwu (1975) observes. But he differs from Nwachukwu (1975) in that he distinguished between qualificative nominals and pure adjectives. Pure adjectives all have fixed positions but not so with qualificative nominals. He gives the following examples:

- (2) a. *Ogologo ulo à* 'the height of the building'
 Length house this
- b. *Ulo' ogologo à* 'this tall building' (Emenanjo 1978:48)
 House length this

The data in (2) is correct, acceptable and well-formed in the language. And forms like that are considered in detail in this study. Again, Emenanjo (1978) defines the notion of a head and its modifier thus:

Nominal modifiers is a cover term for those qualifying words which even though they only occur in the NP, can never be used alone in a minimal NP. They only modify nominals, especially nouns.
 (Emenanjo 1978:70).

Some modifiers certainly cannot minimally occur as single lexical items except they are modifying other elements as Emenanjo (1978) observed above. That observation could have made him to omit many such modifiers in his analysis of noun nominal modifiers. Some quantifiers such as: *ufodu*, *otutu*, *imirikiti*,

iemole, obyla, and numerals are omitted possibly because they sometimes minimally stand as NPs. He analyses the pronouns modifying the nouns as pronominal modifiers even though they can in given cases minimally stand. If the pronouns that modify nouns are pronominal modifiers, it follows that other elements that modify the noun are modifiers whether they can stand alone or not. Whatever flaw one may identify, Emenanjo (1978) stands out in its treatment of nominal modification, considering his NP schema given in (J) above.

Oluikpe's (1978) *English in Igboland* achieved its focus in presenting a bilingual study text for Igbo learners of English. The text apart from achieving a bilingual prescriptive objective, at the same time, presents a theory-based description of the Igbo phrase structure cutting across various grammatical classes in the language. However, the side by side analysis of two disparate languages does not allow the author to focus on a detailed analysis of the Igbo syntax and there is no serious discussion on modifiers. Oluikpe (1979) gives an NP rule with an obligatory N, an optional (N) which modifies the first N, and an optional determiner. This is shown in (3).

(3) NP $\rightarrow$ N (N) (Det) (Oluikpe 1979:21)

Oluikpe's NP schema shows the projecting N to be phrase initial and the modifying elements to be post-head position. This schema accounts only for the noun-noun and determiner structure, but does not account for other possible structures of the Igbo Noun phrase structure possibly because of the evolving nature of the model of the theory he used.

Anagbogu (1990) focuses on providing an adequate description of the regular processes of Igbo nominalizations in Igbo based on Chomsky's (1972) lexicalist hypothesis. The study adequately describes the process of nominalizations in Igbo focusing on the rules generating two major semantic featured classes of nominal [$\pm$ concrete]. In spite of the depth of detail in this work, it does not fully treat the aspects of modification of the noun and that is possibly because the focus was on nominal compounds. Its treatment of modifiers is limited to nominalizations. He differentiates between NP modification and nominal modification saying that the NPs take various kinds of modifiers, including adjectival modifiers, but the nominalizations mostly reject adjectival modifiers. And this is correct. He gave examples as in (4).

(4) a. Nwokē *ocha* b́jara.

Man white come(rv)

'The faircomplexioned man came'

b. **o*-chọ egō *ocha* b́jara.

Pref. seek money white come(rv)

'The white money-monger came'

(5) a. E gbùrù ewū *ojī*.

Imp. kill(rv) goat black

'They killed a black goat.'

b. *O-tí *okpọ* *ojī* gbùrù mmady

pref fist black kill(rv) person

'The black boxer killed somebody'

(Anagbogu 1990:65, 66)

The data above is re-written in a Standard form as against the Onitsha dialect form that Anagbogu (1990) uses. The verbs instead of having the *-rv* form as above has the form *-lv* e.g; *bjàlì, gbulu, mwùlù*. Examples (4a and 5a) show instances of nouns modified by adjectives, while (4b and 5b) are ill-formed being nominals modified by adjectives. In all, three kinds of nominal modifiers are treated in his study. They are lexical modifiers, sentential modifiers and abstract nominalizations as modifiers. The examples in (4 and 5) represent lexical modifiers. He did not say anything about the free occurring modifiers. As such, our concern here is to analyze aspects of noun-modifier relations not covered in Anagbogu (1990).

Mba (1999) using the Government and Binding theoretic framework, postulates a schema for the X^0 nominal and its modifying elements in (6).

The schema in (6) differs from Emenanjo's (1) in that while Emenanjo (1978) allows a pre-noun modifier, Mba (1999) disallows pre-noun modifiers which is akin to the 'no adjective' view of Nwachukwu (1975). Although (6) fits in logically to the theoretic demands of GB, the intuition of the native speaker of Igbo faults such analysis. Pre-modifying elements of the noun phrase cannot all become nouns because of their distribution. A more balanced analysis should accept exceptions to the rule. We reject the analysis and rather uphold Emenanjo's analysis in this study.

One other proposition of Mbah (1999) is his recognition of Tone as a functional category. Tone, he asserts, plays an important role in determining functional types of sentences in Igbo. This assertion is incontrovertible but going further to propose a tone phrase makes tone which is a syntactic, semantic and phonological component of the Igbo language to be limited to a mere syntactic process. If tone phrase is a functor, the implication would be as follows: there would be a multiplicity of functors, and; there would be functors terminology clash. Since tone plays roles in relativisation, polar question formation, conditional clause, affirmative and negative constructs, there would be many kinds of Tone Phrases; relative complementizer Tone phrase, polar question Tone phrase, if-conditional tone phrase, affirmative tone phrase, etc; the second implication is viewed with examples below.

- (7) | chọ̀rọ̀ yā } high tone pronoun; declarative
 You want(rv) it
 'You want it'
- (8) | chọ̀rọ̀ ya } low tone pronoun; interrogative
 You want(rv) it
 'Do you want it?'
- (9) Àda chọ̀rọ̀ ya } without pronoun; declarative
 Ada want(rv) it
 'Ada wants it'
- (10) Àda ọ̀ chọ̀rọ̀ ya } with low-tone interrogative marking pronoun.
 Ada (pron) want(rv) it
 'Does Ada want it?'

In examples (7) and (8), tone distinguishes between a declarative and an interrogative, same goes for (9) and (10) where the insertion of a low tone pronoun determines the functional structure of the sentence. It is accepted that interrogatives contain Q-feature which translates to wh-functor, or a 'do insertion' in English depending on the question type. In Igbo, from the examples above, we see that tone variation on the subject pronoun serves to generate a polar question from a declarative sentence, while pronoun insertion is needed if the subject of the declarative sentence is a noun. Even in zero operator relative construction, the Low default tone relativizer serves to indicate an elided relative pronoun. As such we can conclude that low tone is not in itself a syntactic or functional operator, but serves to show a missing functional item which could stand for any of the functional categories in the determiner domain but not tone per se as a category. Thus, Mbah's (1999) rejection of Emenanjo's schema in (1) based on the X' head parameter selection cannot be sustained. His argument that the pre-noun occurrence of the adjective *ajọ* is explained by assuming it to be a noun also seems poorly motivated.

Anurudu (1999) proposes that cases of pre- and post-noun modification can be analyzed by appealing to features. These features he calls [+strong], [-strong], and [±strong]. The work claims that the strong featured modifiers pre-pose, the weak featured ones post-pose while the ones having both features can pre- or post-pose. The problem with that analysis of the phenomenon is that Igbo modifying items do not have any visible morphological agreement markings that could be said to trigger or determine modifier position. Strong features, according to Chomsky (1995), are those formal and morphological aspects of

words responsible for triggering certain syntactic processes in the grammar. They could be morphological, syntactic or phonological features. Case, for instance, is a formal feature that requires a spec-head relationship for its checking. But in the case of modifiers of the N head, we cannot say that case, Tense or any morphological feature is checked by the raising of the modifier in the noun phrase domain to a phrase-initial position. In this study, we support the feature-theoretic approach though with modifications.

Uba-Mgbemena (2006) gives a useful guide for students and teachers of linguistics especially since it is written in the Igbo language. Various aspects of the Igbo phrase structure are described. In identifying the modifiers of the noun just like Emenanjo (1978) which observes the shifting of qualificative nouns with their heads, Uba-Mgbemena further observes that some quantifiers have free distribution with their heads. The quantifiers he observes include: *ufodu*, and *olenòle* (cf.p.36). Such forms are also analyzed in this study.

1.2 AIMS AND OBJECTIVES OF STUDY

1.2.1. BROAD AIMS AND OBJECTIVES

The global focus of this study therefore, is to draw implications that will affect the perception of head-modifier structures in Minimalist circles and, as such, influence the creation of a more universal explanation of language structure. Thus, this study is an attempt to find out whether differences in modification patterns of phrasal heads in Igbo correspond to a wider universal pattern as set forth in the Minimalist Program.

1.2.2. SPECIFIC AIMS AND OBJECTIVES

The specific aims and objectives of this study are:

1. To account for the shifted modifiers in Igbo.
2. To find out whether differences in modification patterns of noun phrasal heads in Igbo correspond to a wider universal pattern as set forth in the Minimalist Program,
3. To test the adequacy of the Minimalist Programme in analyzing Igbo data.
4. To contribute to the knowledge of studies in Igbo.

1.3 RATIONALE

Without doubt, the issue of phrase structure has been over-flogged over the last three decades with no conclusive, all-embracing descriptively and explanatorily adequate theory. Most proponents of current grammatical theories base their findings and postulations on the well-documented languages of the West, especially, English

Thus, the rationale for this study is that there is a need to complement and advance research in the field of syntax using a language other than the languages of the West, to test theoretical postulations in the Minimalist model and to generate a cross-linguistic phrase structure interpretation that can meet both descriptive and explanatory adequacy using reformulated economy assumptions.

1.4 RESEARCH PROBLEMS

One of the main problems this study addresses is the issue of fixed and unfixed position of modifiers in relation to their heads in Igbo. While some modifiers have a fixed position, some others do not have contrary to parameter setting of

Universal Grammar. Chomsky (1981:8, 9) defends parameter setting model of language acquisition giving two types of evidence -positive and negative evidence. A child learning a language sets positive evidence, say for the head parameter, in a language where the head precedes its satellites, that the head must be the first element of the phrase. According to Radford (1997:23), negative evidence comes in the form of self-correction when the child errs in the selection of the right head parameter setting for the language.

(10b) ... N ...

Parameter selection is used in terms of (43), with two possibilities; the child either puts his modifiers before N or after it but what happens where the two options are feasible? This study proposes a principled way of accounting for the seeming parameter violations. Moreover, head-modifier shift is an aspect of the Igbo syntax that has not been given adequate treatment by scholars although it has been mentioned in the literature (Emenanjo 1978, Oluikpe 1979 and Uba-Mgbemena 2006).

1.5 CLAIMS

This study claims that the noun modifier-head positioning in Igbo is undeniably head-first and the cases of pre-posing noun modifiers could be explained as possible re-arrangements within the phrasal domain (tagged modifier-shift) and that it is feature-driven in order to satisfy the requirements of Greed or ESI (Enlightened Self Interest).

Also the work tries to harmonize the divergent views held by Igbo scholars as to what should be the proper account of the noun-heads and their modifiers. This is done by assuming (à la Chomsky 1993) that displacements of elements in the

computational system of human language are feature-driven. Also given that Chomsky (1999) explains certain displacements to be licensed by such discourse features as topic, focus, new and given information, then, it would not be out of place to posit that modifier-shift is one of such cases.

1.6 DATA AND METHODOLOGY

Ten purposively selected Informants were interviewed and library-based data collection method was also employed. Two informants each were selected from the Orlu dialect, Owerri dialect, Anioma dialect, Enugu and Ngwa dialects representing different geographical zones of Igboland. Some data from previous works are also used as well as the researcher's own intuitions.

The method of analysis will involve a copious use of well-formed and ill-formed expressions in the language with tree diagrams, tables and charts where applicable. Since the problem is basically delineating and explaining the fixed and free modification patterns - which we call *modifier-shift*; a systematic presentation of data showing various aspects of the Igbo head-modifier structures, glossing and translating the glossed data to their nearest English meaning is done.

1.7 OUTLINE OF THESIS

Chapter One reviews relevant literature on Igbo grammar as a necessary background to the problem considered in the study, states the purpose and aim of the study; research problems, methodology, claims, outline of the thesis, rationale, research questions, aims and objectives, and conventions. Chapter Two deals with the theoretical orientation and how the problems can be analysed using a given theory of syntax. Chapters Three and Four are devoted

to analysing data in a proposed modified version of the explanations of the workings of the Computational System. Chapter Five summarizes the study.

1.8 RESEARCH QUESTIONS

This study seeks to answer the following questions:

1. Do modification patterns of noun phrasal heads in Igbo correspond to a wider universal pattern as set forth in the Minimalist Program?
2. Are all instances of rearrangements within a phrase triggered by movement operations?
3. How would the language parser in automated language translation programme handle the shifted modifier structures given the possible pre-head and post-head modifications our data exhibit?
4. How can we account for the shifted modifiers in Igbo?

1.9 CONVENTIONS

The official orthography introduced by Onwu Committee (1961) which has eight vowels and twenty eight consonants is adopted here. The vowels and their transcriptions are:

i [i]	ĩ [ĩ]
e [e]	a [a]
o [o]	o [ɔ]
u [u]	u [v]

It has long been established that vowel harmony operates in the language (Williamson 1972; Nwachukwu 1975, Emenanjo 1978, Uwalaka 1981). The vowels: [i], [e], [o] and [u] are produced with an expanded pharynx while [ĩ],

[a], [o] and [v] are produced with a non-expanded pharynx. The first set of vowels co-occur in simple words while the second set of vowels with the exception of [a] can occur in varied environments. This is exemplified below.

[i] e.g. isi 'head'	[i] e.g. jchọ 'to seek'
ise 'five'	isi 'to say'
isò 'to follow'	jlọ 'to marry'
isūsú ọny 'to kiss'	igà 'hand-cuffs'

[e] e.g. efū 'vain'	[a] e.g. aha 'name'
chi 'cow'	agụ 'lion'
èdò 'indigo'	awọ 'frog'
eke 'python'	azụ 'fish'

[o] e.g. Òbì 'personal name'	[o] e.g. ọgọ 'in-law'
Ogè 'time'	ọgwụ 'medicine'
Ogbù 'dumbness'	ọny 'mouth/hole'

[u] e.g. ùdù 'clay pot, (usually for water)	[v] e.g. ùwà 'world'
Uchè 'mind'	uzọ 'door/way'
Ubi 'farmland'	ụkà 'church'
Úgò 'eagle'	ulọ 'house'

The [a] vowel is the only vowel that can go with some other vowels of different set in simple words as in:

Akpàtì, 'box'

Afè, 'a shirt'

Akpe, 'a river bank'

Ako, 'lignite'

Akpò, 'hard palate'

We argue that, following Emerianjo (1996), the [i] set of vowels are impressionistically the heavy vowels, while the [I] set are called the light vowels. However, it is important to note that vowel harmony does not operate within compound, complex, or borrowed words. This is exemplified in the following words:

Wèta	take-come, 'bring'	(verb) compound
Patùo	carry-down 'bring down'	(verb) compound
Òmenaàlà	'custom'	complex word
Mahadum	'university'	coined word

The emphasized vowels are those that belong to different harmony groups. Vowel harmony does not apply to compound, complex, or borrowed words because they do not fall within its scope or domain of operation. The domain of vowel harmony is the simple two-syllable words but not complex words.

1.10.1 CONSONANTS

The consonants of Igbo, as in the orthography of most other Benue-Congo languages, are represented by both single letters and digraphs. The single letters include: b, d, f, g, h, j, k, l, m, n, ñ, p, r, s, t, v, w, y, z; while the digraphs include: gb, gh, kp, sh, ch, gw, kw, nw, and ny. The letters given above are the ones found in the standard Igbo orthography and they are the only ones that will

be used in this work. In the event that a dialectal variant is used, it will be indicated.

1.10.2 TONE

Pitch variation which affects the meaning of words, phrases and sentences is a common feature of most indigenous Nigerian languages. With the exception of Fulfulde and Nembe, most other indigenous Nigerian languages use tone as a lexical and syntactic distinctive apparatus (Emenanjo, 1978). There cannot be any meaningful study of any aspect of Igbo grammar without a consideration of tone (Uwalaka, 1997). Igbo is said to have a terraced level tone system (Hyman 1988). There is a binary tone system having high and low tones. High tones are predominant in most words and there are instances of high-lowering which is called in the literature as down-stepped highs. Down-stepped tones may be triggered by the need to obey Obligatory Contour Principle (OCP). This principle was first proposed by Leben (1973) to forbid two identical tones from being adjacent at the melodic level in the analysis of Tiv Verbal system. He claimed that a sequence on the tones such as HHL is impossible in the language because the principle rules it out. Goldsmith (1976:36) calls it the Obligatory Contour Principle (OCP).

Obligatory Contour Principle (Goldsmith 1976):

At the melodic level of the grammar, any two adjacent tonemes must be distinct. Thus HHL is not possible melodic pattern; it automatically simplifies to HL.

We thus assume that downstepped tone is as a result of the inability of the melodic level of the grammar in Igbo to allow HH adjacent tonemes. This is purely conjectural. The principle is not widely accepted.

Uwalaka (1997:26) succinctly puts it this way:

17. As we have already noted, Igbo has the distinctive feature of downstep, i.e. a downstepping of a high tone after another high tone. We do not regard this as a mid tone. This is because whereas sequences of low-low, low-high, high-high, high-low occur in Igbo, we do not get mid-mid or mid-high. Downstep is restricted to occurrence after a high tone.

Thus, (17) shows there are high, low, and down-stepped tones in the language. The high notes are marked with an acute accent /'/, the low tone with a grave accent /`/ and the down stepped tone with a macron /-/. Since the downstepped tone is distinctively significant in the language, it follows that it is a distinct tone though it occurs in given environment.

This study adopts the tonal convention of Green and Igwe. The Green and Igwe convention, simply put, could be an application of the marked and unmarked principle of features. A preponderance of a feature is said to be unmarked while a marked feature is a feature that is not widespread. There are fewer marked features in a given system. The marked feature as far as Igbo tone system is concerned is the low and the down-stepped tones. Given that high tones are predominant in Igbo tone system, the Green and Igwe tone marking system leaves out the marking of high tones while it marks the low and down-stepped tones. We adopt the convention because it seems have a better description of the tone system of the language; and makes tone marking easier to apply and understand. High tones will therefore not be marked. Low and down-stepped tones will be appropriately marked with a grave accent or a macron as the case may be.

2.11. DEFINITIONS

- **Movement:** a lexical or syntactic object is termed *moved* if it is displaced from its underlying form (using an old concept) in the syntax of the language or copies to a higher node in the hierarchy to achieve certain system requirements of the grammar.
- **Shifted:** In this study a modifier is assumed *shifted, switched, swapped or free* if it is moved or displaced (copied) from its canonical position in relation to the head of the phrase given parametric setting of the language. Any modifier, whether lexical or phrasal, whose relation to the head is such that it can be positioned to the left is said to be shifted. We also distinguish between obligatory modifier shift and optional modifier shift.
- **Head:** In the sense that some heads in theory are null, some lexical and some others functional, and considering the complementary definitions we have examined above, we assume a combination of the various definitions for our work here and define three-pronged view of headedness. One, the head is a functional feature that determines the referential index of the phrase. Two, the head is the semantic element which all other elements expand. Three the head is the element which occupies a dominant position in the phrase copies (will be made explicit in the analysis).
- **Modifier:** In this study, we use the term modifier to include all words and grammatical combination of words that extend or add meaning to the head whether functional or notional heads.

- Features: Following minimalist assumptions, *features* are indivisible atoms of linguistic expressions which could be formal or lexical. Formal features refer to the phi-features interpretable as, person, number, gender, or case features, while lexical features refer to the the binary feature composition of lexical items expressed in terms of having the feature [$\pm$ N and $\pm$ V]. In this study, we assume a sub-feature of formal feature *measure* such as those indicating number, intensity, continuance, extent, etc.

1.12 SUMMARY

In this chapter, we note that the controversy over the proper realization of the head-modifier positioning stems from a limited understanding of the features and forms of the head and its modifying elements. Attempts have been made to force the modificational system of Igbo to conform to given theoretical models and thus giving rise to the head being seen in terms of positions within the structure.

Given the contributions of various scholars to the issue through the literature reviewed in section 1.1, one is not left in doubt as to the need for a detailed study on the issue of shifted modifying lexical items in the language. And given the models of grammar available to scholars at different times, this study explores the possibility of modifying the new with the old so as to achieve a more comprehensive and dependable solution to the problem of headedness and endocentricity.

CHAPTER TWO

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

2.0 INTRODUCTION

In this chapter, we present a theory which sees language as an optimal design that meets the interface levels - the Minimalist Program. As it stands, two minimalist ideas have been developed over time. One is the greed-theoretic form of Chomsky (1993) which has culminated in the more bio-linguistic oriented version as contained in Chomsky (1999, 2000, 2001, and 2005). We consider them here in terms of old and new Minimalism. However, reference will be made from time to time where necessary to other generative models that were developed before the Minimalist Program.

2.1 FROM GB TO THE MINIMALIST PROGRAM

According to Chomsky (1997:171), the Minimalist program continues the trend in syntactic theory begun in the late 1970s- the move from specific grammatical rules that describe particular syntactic constructions to the general principles that interact to explain syntactic phenomena. That gives a bird's eye view of how the Minimalist Program (MP) conceptualizes grammatical representations and their well-formedness. MP reduces the set of four levels of representation: D-structure, S-structure, Logical form and Phonological form of GB theory to a binary interface levels of PF and LF. PF is connected to the articulatory-perceptual systems while the LF interfaces with the conceptual-Intentional system of cognition.

Apart from the reduction in levels of representation, MP invokes a number of economy principles such as shortest move, procrastinate, and greed. These principles compare derivations involving the same set of lexical resources and discard all but the most economical derivations. This version of Chomsky's grammar grows out of considerations of the workings of mechanisms like movement and of principles like the Case filter. Move- α operates freely in standard GB but in the MP framework movement is for a reason- to have case and phi features checked. Any NP may move to get Case and thus pass the Case filter.

However, a number of conceptual issues are carried over to MP from GB. One, certain locality principles (e.g. Subjacency Condition) correspond to a Least Effort requirement of the Minimalist Program. NP and wh- movement target the first potential position up from the extraction point. Two, operations other than NP or wh- movement are said to have a Last Resort option, e.g. the dummy 'do' insertion in English is a **last resort** option when all other means of satisfying the need for a filled auxiliary node to be used for polar question fails. Least effort and Last resort options suggest a striving for the most economical and minimal way of satisfying principles. Thus MP relies heavily on economy principles in evaluating derivations.

2.1.1 SUMMARY OF CHANGES FROM GB TO MP

The move towards minimizing principles and grammatical constructs seems to a large extent a major landmark achieved in the Minimalist Program. In GB syntax, the load is on four levels of representation but in MP theory, the well-formedness of derivations is determined at the interface between the PF and LF. Other models such as, GB relied on four levels of representation, namely; D-

and S-structure, PF and LF and Aspects model relied on Deep and Surface Structure, the Phonological and Semantic components. But the PF and LF interfaces are the only surviving levels of representation in the Minimalist Program. In summary, the major changes from GB to Minimalism include:

- (i) Constituents move for a reason
- (ii) Grammaticality depends on a comparison of derivations, not on the evaluation of a particular derivation in isolation;
- (iii) Principles apply only at the interface levels of PF and LF, or at both levels. (Weinberg, 2004)

In other words, any instance of movement must be for a reason going by the Minimalist Program contrary to the GB syntax where **Move** alpha 'moves anything anywhere' with no reason given for movement. The grammaticality of any derivation is determined by operations in line with economy principles applying at the two interfaces or at both interfaces. This appears to be an oversimplification and may not fully be supported by cross-linguistic data. However, before we delve into that debate, let us outline the principles as Chomsky 1993, 1995 and 1997 put it.

2.2 MINIMALIST PRINCIPLES

From the previous section, we note that Least effort and Last resort conditions translate to principles guiding or rather constraining derivations. One word for these principles is economy. There are three major economy principles according to (Chomsky 1993) namely; shortest move, greed, and procrastinate.

apart from the reduction in levels of representation, MP invokes a number of economy principles such as shortest move, procrastinate, and greed. These principles compare³ derivations involving the same set of lexical resources and discard all but the most economical derivations. This version of Chomsky's grammar grows out of considerations of the workings of mechanisms like movement and of principles like the Case filter. Move- α operates freely in standard GB but in the MP framework movement is for a reason- to have case and phi features checked. Any NP may move to get Case and thus pass the Case filter.

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2.2.2 SHORTEST MOVE

Shortest Move is said to be the most technically specific economy principle and takes over much of the work performed by Relativized Minimality (Rizzi, 1990), ~~minimality~~, and the head movement constraint in the earlier versions of P & P theory. The idea presented here is that a constituent must move to the first position of the right kind up from its source position. The examples in 1(a and b) taken from Marantz (1995:355) show instances of shortest move violations.

1. (a) **what_i did you persuade who to buy t_i*

Who_i did you persuade t_i to buy what?

- (b) **Have_i John will t_i left by the time we get there?*

Will_i John t_i have left by the time we get there? (Marantz, 1995)

The application of shortest move is restricted to the type of constituents moving and to the relevant landing sites. Heads are prohibited from skipping over any head position in between. The derivation in (1a) crashes because the wh-element *what* is barred from moving from the foot of the tree to the head of the chain skipping over another head *who*. In (1b) *have* cannot skip the head position occupied by *will* to move to a higher head position. In the same way, movement of wh-elements must not skip over the specifier position of CP.

2.2.2 PROCRASTINATE

Procrastinate is a principle that prefers derivations that postpone movement until after spell-out, so that the result of such movements does not affect PF. It requires that features which do not need to be checked overtly must be checked covertly after spell-out and before LF. At LF, all relevant features must already have been checked. A derivation yields legitimate structural description at LF only if that structural description is made entirely of "legitimate objects" (Chomsky 1997:194). Only legitimate objects have interpretation at the interfaces. In English, according to Radford (1997), movement of main verbs to tense is disallowed until after spell-out; showing the operation of *Procrastinate*. In French, on the other hand, the main verb need not stay action on movement but is permitted by the computation to move before spell-out.

2.2.3 GREED

Greedy, according to Chomsky (1993, 1994) states that movement of an item α is driven exclusively by α 's own requirements even if failure to move causes the derivation to crash. The intuitive force of Greedy has been acknowledged by critics such as Lasnik (1995). Lasnik challenges the *selfish* interpretation of Greedy by Chomsky stating that movement is not always for selfish reasons. Lasnik states his position with an alternative explanation of the principle of Greedy in the form of what he calls "Enlightened Self Interest". We discuss the two positions immediately as captured in (2).

- (2) a. Greedy: Movement of α to B is for the satisfaction of formal requirements of α (Chomsky 1993).

- b. 'Enlightened Self Interest': Movement of α to β must be for the satisfaction of formal requirements of α or β (Lasnik 1995:66).

Lasnik favors (2b) over (2a) due to the inability of Greed to account for case and agreement properties of existential constructions and the inconsistencies of the Q-feature checking in multiple wh interrogations. Chomsky (1986a) argues that the associate of *there*, in this case, *a man*, moves to the position of *there* in LF in such a sentence as (3).

- (3) There is a man here.
(4) a. There is/*are a man here (*is a man here.)
b. There are/*is men here. (*are men here.)

According to Lasnik, there is a bizarre agreement paradigm in (4) if movement was solely for selfish requirements of the associate of *there* not considering that movement could be for the satisfaction of both features of the moved item and the host. The associate of *there*, *a man*, does not move solely for the satisfaction of its own features, but for the overall convergence of the sentence. If it fails to move, the whole sentence fails to converge; but if it moves, the sentence converges. This may be to satisfy EPP requirements and not selfish requirements of the associate of *there*.

The second consideration is that multiple wh-elements in a sentence would be problematic to explain given Greed. If WH elements have Q-features to check via movement, why does only one raise to check its features while the others remain *in situ*? How do you determine which one checks its Q-feature and what happens to the ones not checking the features? Example (5) shows an instance of the failure of movement to check wh- features.

- (5) * what did who buy (Lasnik 1995:64).

If indeed the situation is so, Lasnik argues, the two *wh*-elements in (5) should move. Elements move when there is an overall usefulness both to the moved item and or to the destination of movement. Definitely there is a problem of determining which of the *wh*-elements checks its Q-feature, since they are assumed to have Q-features that must be checked through movement. Lasnik argues that the relaxation of the principle, Greed, to include ESI (that is, movement for altruistic purposes) would remove the problem of checking Q-features. It simply involves a movement of the most appropriate *wh*-element for the overall convergence of the expression. All that needs to be said is that interrogative C has the Q-feature, that the feature is strong, and that it can be checked by any *wh*-operator, and that the Q-feature of the operator need not be checked (it can survive to the interface level) (Lasnik 1995).

This is a plausible argument when tested with data from Igbo as (6) depicts. The examples in (6a and b) have the same semantic content but different structural descriptions. We note that the *wh*-operator, *gini*, can remain in situ, as in (6a) or move to the Spec. of CP as in the case of (6b). There is no strong Q feature of C to be checked in Igbo, as such, the movement of *gini* to the Spec of CP in (6b) is optional. In other words, movement in this instance is not for the selfish needs of the *wh*-operator, *gini*, nor for the needs of C, since C is weak in the language. Further examples show that any of the operators in a double *wh*-operator sentence may move with little or no semantic change as in (7) and (8).

- (6) a. Ebò mèrè gini?
PN do (past) what (*wh*-operator)
'Ebo did what?'

b. Gini ká Ebō m̀èrè?
Wh-operator comp. PN do (past)
'What did Ebo do?'

(7) a. Ònye m̀èrè gini taa?
Who do(past) what today
Who did what today?

b. Gini m̀èrè ònye taá?
What do (past) who today
What happened to whom today?

(8) a. Ònye m̀èrè gini n'èbèè
Who do (past) at where
'Who did what where?'

b. À sị nà e m̀èrè ònye gini n'èbèè?
Imp. Say comp. imp.-do (past) who, what, where.
'Did they say who did what at what place?'

c. ? À sị nà e m̀èrè gini ònye n'èbèè?
Imp. say comp. imp.-do(past) what who, where

d. À sị nà gini ká e m̀èrè ònye n'èbèè?
Imp.say comp. what comp. imp.-do (past) who at where
'Did they say what happened to whom at what place?'

e. À sị nà ònye ká e m̀èrè gini n'èbèè?
Imp. say that who that imp.-do(past) what at where
'Did they say whom what happened to at what place?'

The data in (8) show that a wh-operator can skip over another wh-position and the sentence still converges. The locative wh-operator, realized here as a preposition modifier, cannot move presumably because its Q-features are only satisfied *in situ*.

Thus, wh-movement, as Lasnik argues, may not be for the satisfaction of personal features but for the convergence of the whole expression. Examples (8a) through (8e) show instances of double or multiple wh-operators in which any one of the closest operators moves. (8c.) is less acceptable than (8b.), while (8d.) and (8e.) permit variation in the hierarchy of wh-operator occurrences.

Let us elucidate further with a tree diagram of (7a) as (8f).

From the tree diagram (8f), we note the wh- elements are *in situ* within the IP. The Spec-CP is not filled since there is no need for movement here. However, any of the wh- elements may move to Spec-CP when there is an overt complementizer as in (8g).

The diagram in (8g) shows that Greed triggers movement when the complementizer node is filled but does not have to move anything when the complementizer node is empty as in (8f). As a result, we support the argument in favor of a relaxed principle of Greed in which movements are not all made on the basis of selfish needs. But before we explore the argument advanced here against Greed or for ESI, we will immediately describe the organization of grammar in the Minimalist Program and try as much as possible to define our concepts and understanding of the workings of the computational system and adapt it to fit our purposes in this study.

2.3 ORGANIZATION OF THE MINIMALIST PROGRAM

The organization of grammar in the *Minimalist Program* is somewhat similar to that obtained in its predecessor-GB, except that there is a reduction in the levels of representations.

Figure 1: Organisation of MP Lexical Resources

(Adapted from Marantz 1995)

As sketched in fig. 1, the model is a representation of what Chomsky calls the computational system of human languages (CH_i). The human mind (language faculty) is seen as a complex computer machine that processes language. The lexicon houses the lexical resources with which derivations are realized. Each item is assumed to have an entry form $[P, S, F]$, where components of P serve to yield λ (phonological features) and components of S serve only to yield π (semantic features), and components of F (formal features), e.g. the categorial features $[\pm N, \pm V]$ which may enter into the computation but must be eliminated (at least by PF) for convergence (Chomsky 1995:394).

In this model, derivations start from a set of lexical resources. Computation involves putting lexical items together and comparing among computations in the same set of lexical items. The lexical items are joined in pair-wise merger operations to form phrases and sentences. Thus operations *select* and *merge* ensure that the right concatenation of words and phrases is carried out. Words and phrases so formed are submitted to the interface levels one at a time for checking of features.

2.4 PHRASE STRUCTURE IN THE MINIMALIST MODEL

The question we need to answer here is how the Minimalist Program views structuralization in terms of headedness and endocentricity, functional vs. lexical categories, the relation of argument structure to syntactic structure, and the status of the X-Bar theory in the current model. We will take them in the order they are listed.

2.4.1 HEADEDNESS AND ENDOCENTRICITY

We have already stated that the main components of the grammar include the structure-building operations of Merge and Move, feature checking through movement to functional categories, the interfaces and the economies of derivation and representation. The notion of the head of projection or phrase is primal to all generative models. A head is generally taken to be the lexical item which determines the syntactic nature of a larger unit (a phrase) of which **head** is part.

* feature-based definition of head as in GB theoretic form sees head as a composition of features, namely, $[\pm N, \pm V]$. A head in this regard is seen as a bundle of features (Matushanky, 2001) which componentially is interpreted to have four possible lexical outputs as in (9).

⇒ Noun = $[+N -V]$

Verb = $[-N +V]$

Adjective = $[+N +V]$

Preposition = $[-N -V]$ (Haegemann 1991)

Thus a noun phrase is headed not by a noun per se but a feature bundle which in this case is $[+N -V]$. The same goes for other categories in (9). However, are all structures endocentric? In other words, does every phrase have a unique head? Yes. Works in Principles and Parameters assume that endocentricity holds for every phrase in languages (Chomsky 1986a, Speas 1990, Haegemann 1991, and Chomsky 1995).

Chomsky (1993, 1995 and 1997) assumes that syntactic structures are built by taking smaller structures and combining them by a computational operation, starting with items selected from the lexicon. He argues that if operation 'select' picks two lexical items α and β , there are three possible representations for the structure of Σ (a merger of α and β).

(10) (a) the intersection of α and β

(b) the union of α and β

(c) one or the other of α and β (Chomsky 1997:244)

Excluding (10a and b) we are left with (10c) as the only possible structure of any phrase in any language. (10a) is rejected because an intersection of α and β

is not possible, while (10b) is rejected because a union of α and β will make both items lose their separate identities. (10c) is preferred based on the fact that any of the items can project, be it α or β , other principles determining the head-modifier positions in any given language e.g. parameter setting. The schema in (11) shows the tree diagrams for the structures in (10c).

From (11) we see that it is either α projects or β projects and the real language example in (11i) shows that it is either the N ulo projects or the D $\hat{a}$ projects. The two cannot project at the same time. The projecting item is assumed to be the head of the phrase in accordance with the uniqueness condition which states:

(11ii) Every phrase is projected by a unique category. (cf. Brody 1998)

No phrase can be headed by two categories at the same time, for it will amount to violating the uniqueness condition. Structure building therefore, revolves around select, merge and move. The atomic syntactic units (lexical items) are selected, merged and moved to generate convergent derivations. Also phrases so formed via merge are consequently merged and moved to generate larger structures. Given phrase structures A and B, we can combine the two into a larger structure C yielding the structure $[C A B]$ with labels for C, A and B given

in an X' format. Merge and move would generate something like in (12) and (13).

(12) Merge:

A and B may be lexical items or complex phrases, and Merge combines them to create a new structure C. Operation Move takes a substructure A of B and creates a new structure of C which has a copy of A as immediate substructures with labels A, B and C consistent with X' theory as in (13).

(13) Move:

We notice that the only difference between merge and move is that while merge acts upon separate structures, move acts upon structures where one dominates the other. Be that as it may, Merge and Move are complementary. The moved subset of B leaves a trace at the extraction point showing a link between the chain {A, t_A}. Thus, the head of the given phrase remains unchanged. However, Williams (1994) and Bouchard (1995) see headedness differently. Bouchard (1995:75, 459) proposes a parameter of "endocentricity value" by which specific languages allow only one or more than one head. Williams (1994:11) argues specifically that coordinate structures and clauses are doubly headed.

The idea of non-unique head as put forward by Williams (1994) and Bouchard (1995) seems plausible considering the facts of shifted modifiers in Igbo and the

seeming double headed nature of coordinate structures as noted by Williams. But this view violates the uniqueness condition and entails passing the structure in (14) as well-formed. However, with the advent of functional categories, coordinate structures can very well be assumed to be under one unitary head-conjunction, or *ConjP*. If this assumption is correct, then doubly headed phrases, such as the conjoined noun phrases, could be accounted for.

(15)a. Òbi nà Àda
 PN Conj. PN
 'Obi and Ada'

We note that (15a) is well-formed and yet the representation of its tree diagram in (15b) is ill-formed since it has non-unique head contrary to the uniqueness condition. If *ConjP* is ruled out because it does not conform to the tenets of the X-bar or head parameter setting for languages, then one option that can be explored is to argue that the first of the conjoined nouns heads the phrase for a head-first language, while the second noun heads the phrase in a head-last language. That option too is ruled out since the conjunction may as well head the other conjoint. We will return to this issue in the closing chapter.

2.4.2 FUNCTIONAL VS. LEXICAL CATEGORIES

The main breakthrough which the Principles and Parameters approach bequeathed to the Minimalist program is the concept of functional categories. Traditionally some categories were thought to carry lexical content information while some others carry only functional or grammatical information. The divide was then between open class or lexical items and the closed class or functional items. Lexical items include: nouns, verbs, adjectives, adverbs, and prepositions. The functional items include: determiners, complementizers, Infl, and perhaps conjunction. However, many other functional categories have been recognized in current linguistic works. Starting with Chomsky (1986), we consider briefly the evolution of functional projections.

2.4.3 THE GENERALIZATIONS

We consider here some of the generalizations of the theory that are used to explain how language works in this model.

2.4.3.1 THE INFL AND COMP. GENERALIZATION

In Chomsky (1981) and Stowell (1981), it is suggested that the syntactic constituents with label S and S' which pose a problem for endocentric analysis might better be seen as headed by INFL and COMP, respectively, but it was not until Chomsky (1986a) that they were accorded full projection status in the form of functional categories. Chomsky asks whether the system regulating Lexical Categories "extend[s] to the non-lexical categories as well..." He answers; "evidently, the optimal hypothesis is that it does", Chomsky (1986a); hence he, sort of, posits a full functional category status for the IP and CP.

2.4.3.2 THE DP AND OTHER FUNCTORS

In his unpublished MIT dissertation, Steven Abney carried on the generalization to include the DP as a projection of the determiner. Pollock, on the other hand, split IP into AGRP and AGR (agreement). There has been a flurry of suggestions for the inclusion of NEGP, for negation, ASPP, for aspects and, in fact, some linguists made use of them in their works. Abney (1987:64, 65) lists some properties which he thinks are not criterial for classification as a functional element.

- (i) Functional Elements constitute closed lexical classes.
- (ii) Functional Elements are generally phonologically and morphologically dependent. They are generally stressless, often clitics or affixes, and sometimes even phonologically null.
- (iii) Functional Elements permit only one complement, which is in general not an argument. The arguments are CP, PP, and ... DP. Functional elements select IP, VP, and NP.
- (iv) Functional Elements are usually inseparable from their complement.
- (v) Functional Elements lack ... "descriptive content". Their semantic contribution is second-order, regulating or contributing to the interpretation of their complement. They mark grammatical or relational features, rather than picking out a class of objects.

We note that (iii) is theory-internal and the rest state known facts about functional elements. Abney (1987:57-58) takes (v) to be the central characteristic crucial for motivating distinction between c-projection and s-projection (where c- refers to categorical projection and s- to semantic

projection). Functional categories being dependent on the semantic projection of lexical categories have no s-projection of their own. Thus functional categories (FCs) are part of the s-projections of lexical Heads. The distinction between C-, S-, and f-projections is his way of characterizing the syntactic (Categorical), lexical (semantic), and purely functional projections. This, in a nutshell, is Abney's idea of functional and lexical categories.

Abney's generalization that quantifiers, numerals, determiners and wh-elements are all subsumed under one umbrella term, D-projection, is weakened by the fact that they have differing occurrences in the language. However, on a closer look, one discovers that the shifted modifiers have a consistent position in the grammar of Igbo and that the pure determiners never move. The N-N shift occurs within the D-projection and not N-projection. This distinction is necessary to achieve explanatory adequacy. Spencer (1992:313) calls the general idea the Full Functional Projection Hypothesis (FFPH) stated as in (17).

(17) Full Functional Projection Hypothesis

Any morphosyntactic formative which corresponds to a Functional Category in a given language is syntactically the head of maximal projection.

No doubt the divide between lexical and grammatical items is being eroded by the FFPH. The question we ask is this: why must functional items be given full projection status?

The answer possibly is so as to facilitate an identical phrasal relation in both classes of items. What then is the difference between lexical and functional items? Fukui and Speas (1986), Fukui (1995), and Speas (1990) proffer some

Fukui and Speas (1986) advance four properties contrasting lexical categories with functional ones.

- (18) (i) Functional Heads have one and only one (i.e., non-iterable) Specifier, while the Specifiers of Lexical Heads may be iterable ones. The Specifiers of Functional Heads are often (in our model, always) moved from within their complement.
- (ii) All Functional Heads can have Specifier positions; it is not at all clear that all Lexical Heads have Specifier positions.
- (iii) Languages which lack Functional Heads also lack Specifier positions.

Fukui (1995:12, 13) also adds the observation that functional categories do not have theta-grids of Lexical Conceptual Structures. He probably was building on Abney's position that functional categories lack semantic content being closed class items. Fukui represents this as in (19).

(19)

	C	I	DET
Kase assigner	+WH	Tense/AGR	's
Non-Kase assigner	That	To	The

(Fukui 1995)

In the table above Fukui avers that Kase assigning functors include; **+wh**, **T/AGR** and the genitive **'s** clitic, while the non-Kase assigning functors include; **that**, **to** and **the**. Granted that the genitive clitic assigns the genitive case, a feature taken care of by tone and 'modifier positioning' in Igbo, the case assigning wh-element and even T and AGR are still purely speculative.

may, the arguments for the adoption of functional projections has gained wide acceptance from generative grammarians.

2.4.3.3 STRUCTURE AND ARGUMENT-HOOD

How does lexical information get structured in the syntax? What is the relationship between syntactic structure and individual lexical requirements? Chomsky (1981) suggested that syntactic subcategorization information is structuralized as D-structure using defined predicates such as "government" to regulate the mapping. Grimshaw (1979, 1981) argues that as well some sort of semantic selection was required in the lexicon and in structuralization. Chomsky (1986b), drawing on David Pesetsky's unpublished 1982 MIT dissertation, argues that only the semantic selection (S-selection) was redundant. Rothstein (1991a, 1991b) counters that not all C-selection is in fact eliminable. Chomsky (1981, 1986b) also suggests that D-structure is "a pure representation of theta structure" (1986:100). This idea is taken up and its implications extensively traced out by Speas (1990). However Baker (1988) in his Uniform Thematic Assignment Hypothesis (UTAH) (20) makes a proposal on argument alignment, and Bouchard (1991) also makes a similar proposal which he calls Relative Theta Assignment Hypothesis (RTAH), given in (21).

- (20) UTAH: Identical thematic relationships between items are represented by identical structural relationship between those items at the level of D-structure. (Baker: 1988)
- (21) RTAH: the argument which is relatively highest in Lexical Conceptual Structure is linked to the position which is relatively highest in syntactic structure, and so forth, for the second highest, etc. (Bouchard 1991:28-29).

The central idea is that thematic information is unavoidably uniform regardless of movement. This is a reformulation of theta criterion that every argument is assigned one and only one theta role. The Minimalist Program dispenses with

theta role assignment preferring that lexical items are projected to the computation with roles already specified.

2.4.4 X' THEORY IN THE MINIMALIST MODEL

Stowell (1981) begins the concept of "X-bar reduction" which reached its zenith in Speas (1990). With the introduction of an independent lexicon in Chomsky (1965) the grammar contained a lot of redundancy, for the same information was specified in both the phrase structure rules and subcategorization frames. Consequently, phrase structure rules were eliminated in the P & P model for the X' theoretic framework which also had its own rules. Chomsky (1995, 1997:242) argues for a non-X-bar theoretic approach which he calls the bare output conditions.

(22) At the LF interface, it must be possible to access a lexical item LI and its non-phonological properties LF(LI): the semantic properties and the formal properties that are interpreted there..., given the inclusiveness condition, minimal and maximal projections are not identified by any special marking, so they must be determined from the structure in which they appear.... There are no such entities as XP (X^{max}) or (X^{min}) in the structures formed by C_{HL} , though I continue to use the formal notations for expository purposes, along the lines of X' (X-bar) for any other category. A category that does not project any further is a maximal projection XP, and one that is not a projection at all is a minimal projection X^{min} ; any other is an X', invisible at the interfaces for computation. Chomsky (1997:242)

(22) Predicts that the computation is blind to intermediate levels but accesses the lexical and categorial levels in the interfaces. The continued use of the X' schema is purely for expository purposes and has no theoretical consequence. This is the position we adopt in our analysis in this work.

2.4.5 THE BARE PHRASE STRUCTURE

The notion of a bare phrase structure (Chomsky 1994), was introduced to solve the problem of multiplicity of structures occasioned by the use of intermediate nodes. The head node is the element that is the terminal element having no parts but features.

- (23) ...terminal element LI is an item selected from the numeration, with no parts (other than features) relevant to C_{HL} . A category $X^{[m]}$ is a terminal element, with no categorial parts. We restrict the term head to terminal elements. Chomsky (1997:245)

The bare phrase structure is best defined in terms of the notion of the head as exemplified in (23). The head of a phrase is defined as a terminal node (which automatically entails that in order to be distinguished from terminals, non-terminal nodes must contain more information than what heads contain (Chomsky (1994). Matushansky (2003) defines head as syntactically indivisible bundle of features. This agrees with Chomsky's assertion that: if constituents α , β of K are formed in the course of computation, one of the two must project. It is either α or β projects. This conforms to the uniqueness condition stated in (11). Instead of having a category level representation in, say; *the book*, we should have a straightforward representation as in (23), Chomsky's

- (24). a.
- (Chomsky 1997:246)

In other words, the functional terms, NP, DP, IP, etc., do not matter much more than having a bare syntax using the terminal elements. The elimination of the standard X' theory in favor of bare essentials as depicted in (24) is Chomsky's way of showing that the intermediate theoretic approach is redundant in the

Minimalist Program and, as such, should be dispensed with and we noted earlier that the Langtech parsing grammar upholds it. Since the bare phrase structure is concerned with making use of the most economical structural schematization, it serves better the purposes of the Minimalist Program; as such we adopt it in this work.

2.4.6 FUNCTIONAL CATEGORIES, FEATURE-CHECKING AND MOVE

The heart of the operations of the Minimalist Program is feature-checking through movement to a checking domain. Various kinds of features must be checked with a head which is lexically allowed to check that feature by virtue of its own intrinsic features. The approved way this is done in this model is to move the category in need of this feature-checking to a checking domain (usually, via a spec-head relation) to the specifier position of the head.

In section 2.1.5, we saw that constituents are said to move for selfish checking reasons (following core Minimalist assumptions) or for the general good according to Lasnik (1995). One thing we can infer is that the two scholars agree that movement is for a reason; it is not redundant. The only problem is whether an item moves so as to check its own features or the features of another.

However, mention is not made in the literature of items that seem to move but for no apparent reason. One such item is the shifted structures presented in this work. There is no doubting the fact that Greed fails to account for shifted structures, as such, we look for a better way as provided by the more recent minimalism.

2.5 IN RECENT MINIMALISM

Just as we have said earlier that Generative Grammar is a grammar in a continuous flux, further modifications of the Minimalist theory have taken place from 1995 to the present time. There is 'Derivation by Phase' (Chomsky 1999), 'Beyond Explanatory Adequacy' (Chomsky 2001), and 'Three Factors in Language Design' (Chomsky 2005), all modifications of the Minimalist Program. Before presenting any of the newer versions, let us itemize the basic concepts in the Minimalist program.

1. *The Minimalist Program posits fewer levels of representation.* As said earlier, levels such as Deep Structure and Surface Structure are removed, on the assumption that such levels were theory-internal in earlier frameworks; they were the levels at which constraints such as the Case Filter and the Theta Criterion were said to hold, and as minimalist theories avoid such constraints, the levels of representation which they required are no longer needed. The argument goes that the only 'conceptually necessary' levels (the only levels with independent motivation) are the levels at which the computational system interfaces with the phonological system (Phonological Form), and the conceptual or semantic system (Logical Form).
2. *Moreover, the framework posits only a few derivational rules,* the main two being Merge - a process to connect elements in a hierarchical manner, and Move - a process to displace elements in the hierarchy to different positions. Also, the program posits fewer steps in a derivation, stating that steps should only be taken where strictly necessary. In other words, any step taken in the course of a derivation must be extremely

necessary. In this framework, a sentence is built up by selecting lexical items from a numeration, or as Berwick (1998) puts it, a 'bag of words': some set of lexical resources which is a subset of the entire lexicon, and continuously applying Merge and Move until the derivation is complete, or in minimalist terminology, until the derivation converges. In other words, the derivation keeps going until all conditions on it have been satisfied.

3. *The MP is a Lexicalist theory of syntax.* By this we mean that all items in the lexicon are specified as having a number of features before they enter the derivation. These features are formal, phonological, or semantic. Phonological and semantic features can be interpreted by the phonological and semantic components respectively, but certain formal features cannot, and so must be removed during the course of the derivation. Formal features are either *interpretable* or *uninterpretable*, the latter being those that must be removed. Removal happens through a process of feature checking.

We can describe this process in the following way: on being selected from the numeration, a lexical item with a formal feature must search the numeration for another item with a matching feature. Once it finds such an item, the two matching features can check. Checking is best understood as a procedure whereby matching features cancel each other out, or dissolve each other away.

4. One stipulation on checking features is that matching features can only check off if they are in a local relation. Thus, we have found the first of two things that regulate the application of the Move operation in this

framework. Feature checking forces Move to apply so that items which need to check with each other can be in a local relation.

5. The second thing to regulate movement is *economy conditions*. These ensure that the movements which take place are the simplest or most economical possible. For example, the Shortest Move Condition says that if there is more than one movement available to us at a certain point in a derivation, we must make the movement which is shortest. So, we can sum up this brief technical introduction by outlining the MP as simply a combination of feature checking and economy constraints. In this framework (as we have seen above) elements move to have some uninterpretable feature checked, that is, the moved element gets a feature checked, not the target.

In his recent work Chomsky (1999, 2001, 2004 and 2005), on the other hand, dispenses with covert LF movement altogether and replaces it with long-distance probe-goal agreement. Probe is explained in terms of the element seeking a merger relation with another, while goal is expressed informally in terms of the target of the probe or search.

The derivation or structure building process proceeds in phases. The input for the derivation, the numeration or lexical array, is divided into sub-arrays which in turn are inputs for sub-derivations. CP, the discourse level (illocutionary force), and vP, the level of predication (argument structure, the "who did what to whom"), are strong phases. Once a phase is completed, the (c-command) *domain* is sent to PF encoding and is therefore not accessible for further syntactic computation. In this model there are multiple Spell-Outs. The *periphery* (specifier and phase X⁰, or edge) is available as part of another sub-

array providing input to the derivation of another phase. The process continues until the (super-) array is emptied. The advantage of this kind of process is that Merge carries the sole operational load of the computational system.

- (25) Reliance on iterable Merge as the sole computational operation of narrow syntax eliminates, as unformulable, the notions d- and s-structure, and three of the compositional operations of EST: those that form d-structure and map it to s-structure, and then on to LF. It also revives, in far more elementary terms, the notion of generalized transformation of the earliest work in generative grammar in the 1950s. A great deal of descriptive capacity is lost by this optimal assumption, including all processes and principles associated with d- and s-structure, bar-level distinctions in phrase structure (N vs. N', etc.), and much else. Since this descriptive technology has been widely and productively used, it is a significant empirical task to show that it is dispensable – to show, that is, that it was misconceived, and should be abandoned. I will assume that success in this endeavor has been sufficient so that it is reasonable to assume it for our purposes here. (Chomsky2004)

In its latest form, the Minimalist Program relies heavily on merge as the sole computational operation of narrow syntax. As (25) shows, Merge revives the notion of generalized transformation of the earliest work in generative grammar in the 50s. Two kinds of Merge are given in Chomsky (2005), namely internal and external Merge (IM and EM).

26. IM yields the ubiquitous displacement phenomenon. At the semantic interface, the two types of Merge correlate well with the duality of semantics that has been studied within generative grammar for almost 40 years, at first in terms of “deep and surface structure interpretation” (and of course with much earlier roots). To a large extent, EM yields generalized argument structure (theta roles, the “cartographic” hierarchies, and similar properties); and IM yields discourse-related properties such as old information and specificity, along with scopal effects. The correlation is reasonably close, and perhaps would be found to be perfect if we understood enough. The two available types of Merge have been treated very differently since the early days of modern generative grammar. But that is a historical residue; we have to ask whether it is accurate. It has always been presupposed without comment that EM comes free: no one has postulated an “EPP property” for EM or stipulated that it satisfies the NTC. IM, in contrast, has been regarded (by me, in particular) as a problematic operation, an “imperfection” of language that has to be postulated as an unexplained property of UG

unless it can be motivated in some principled way. The displacement property of natural language is simply a fact: expressions are commonly pronounced in one place and interpreted in others as well. (Chomsky 2005:7)

The External Merge is the operation between the verb and its complements or objects, or adjuncts in an *in situ* position while the Internal Merge relates to the cases of seemingly moved, topicalized, and focused discourse elements. And this is the aspect of Merge that best explains the permuted structures in Igbo. Without going into much further detail, we characterize how Merge works and how it explains the phenomenon of head-modifier shifting.

➤ Merge can apply freely, yielding expressions interpreted at the interface in many different kinds of ways. They are sometimes called deviant, but that is only an informal notion.

(26) corroborates Cinque's (1996) exposé on the structure of the NP if we apply the freely applying Merge to the data in question. The application of Merge yields expressions like (27 and (28).

27. In $\{H, \alpha\}$, H an LI, H is the label. (Chomsky 2004:10)

28. If α is internally merged to β , forming $\{\alpha, \beta\}$ then the label of β is the label of $\{\alpha, \beta\}$ (Chomsky, 2004:11)

In actual language example, if *oma* is internally merged to *nwoke*, forming $\{oma, nwoke\}$ then the label of *nwoke* is the label of *oma* in the sense that *oma* is subsumed under *nwoke* as its modifier. There is no difference between (27; 28) and the earlier minimalist notion of bare phrase structure save that the operations that generate them differ. While the former merges using a head parameter concept, the latter dispenses with head parameters. The implication of that is that heads need not be restricted to a given position all the time in a given language. IM is said to always leave a copy since Merge applies over and over

again Chomsky 2004:11). A derivation that yields an IM merged object, at some point of the derivation, has applied EM merge, and this is where the copy-erase procedure applies. "External Merge correlates with argument structure. Internal Merge with edge properties, scopal or discourse-related (new and old information, topic etc.) (Chomsky 2005:14)). A rough representation of the Merge relations in diagrams will look like (29).

(29a) follows straightforwardly from (27) and (28). The application of External Merge to the two syntactic objects gives rise to an H labelled and headed structure (29a). The subsequent application of Internal Merge generates a phrase having copies lower in the stratum as in (29b). However, since the system prescribes erasure of copies, (29c) becomes the final output of IM. In other words, using the generalized operation Merge, IM in this case, displacements are accounted for without feature checking. But how does the operation of IM which effectively reverses the position of the head, affect the basic parameter of head first and head last in language? The answer is straightforward. It does not negate parameter selection for movement is head to head (see 2.7, 8).

2.6 MOTIVATION FOR USING THE MINIMALIST PROGRAM

Due to the ever-changing nature of Generative grammar, one is often tempted to question the validity of whatever proposition is put forth by the generativists of the Chomskyan mould. From Syntactic Structure till date, there have been several modifications of the Chomskyan theory such that what we now have as the current theory is completely different from its earlier versions. Moreover, Chomsky himself has long ago said:

- (30) Neither the general theory nor the particular grammars are fixed, for all time... Progress and revision may come from the discovery of new facts about particular languages or from purely theoretical insights about the organization of linguistic structure. (Chomsky 1957:50).

Since a theory that is perfectly descriptively and explanatorily adequate has not yet evolved, and bearing in mind that any meaningful description of language must be based on a particular linguistic model, I consider the Minimalist Program more appropriate for this work. It best explains the issue of modifier-shift in Igbo modifier-head expressions even while retaining the head parameter postulation of core minimalist grammars.

Again, the need to put to test using language specific data, novel generalizations and assumptions of the current linguistic theory, makes the Minimalist Program most fitted for this study. In conclusion, I think that insights gathered from the use of the theory in this work may help further research and development of a more optimal and adequate syntactic theory.

2.7 THE PRESENT WORK

The present work holds that modifier-shift attests to not only the recent language external postulations about the workings of the human faculty of language (VL) but also that features are checked by movement. Three main factors in language description, according to Chomsky (2005) are: (i) the genetic endowment (same as the UG postulations), (ii) experience (not a novel idea from Principles and Parameters) and (iii) external apparatus of language description. The third factor is what makes theoretical linguistics a viable endeavor, using language-independent principles to explain the phenomena of language. The present work offers a minimally complex explanation of the nominal phrase structure adapting generalized findings from Cinque (1996), the feature-theoretic Minimalist Program. Thus, modifier-shift is feature-driven.

Cinque (1996) gives a possible order of elements within the noun phrase domain as it relates to different language types based on Kayne's (1994) Linear Correspondence Axiom but focusing on the noun phrase. (Kayne (1994) postulates Linear Correspondence Axiom, an X-bar theory which holds that there is a given structural form for phrases universally; and that the form is linearly ordered as Specifier-Head-Complement. Deviations from that order are products of movement at one point in time in the evolution of such languages that do not have the Specifier head-complement configuration. This view explains Japanese, for instance, which does not permit Wh movement. The question particle *ka* occurs at the end of sentences. The explanation is that the whole clause is moved to the Specifier of C and that is why the question particle appears last.) There are fourteen attested noun-modifier order in all languages while ten are unattested.

31a.	(i)	DEM NUM A N	attested
	(ii)	DEM NUM N A	attested
	(iii)	DEM N NUM A	attested
	(iv)	N DEM NUM A	attested
b.	(i)	DEM A NUM N	unattested
	(ii)	DEM A N NUM	attested
	(iii)	DEM N A NUM	attested
	(iv)	N DEM A NUM	attested
c.	(i)	NUM DEM A N	unattested
	(ii)	NUM DEM N A	unattested
	(iii)	NUM N DEM A	unattested
	(iv)	N NUM DEM A	unattested
d.	(i)	NUM A DEM N	unattested
	(ii)	NUM A N DEM	attested
	(iii)	NUM N A DEM	attested
	(iv)	N NUM A DEM	attested
e.	(i)	A DEM NUM N	unattested
	(ii)	A DEM N NUM	unattested
	(iii)	A N DEM NUM	attested
	(iv)	N A DEM NUM	attested
f.	(i)	A NUM DEM N	unattested
	(ii)	A NUM N DEM	unattested
	(iii)	A N NUM DEM	attested
	(iv)	N A NUM DEM	attested

(iv) N A NUM DEM attested

(32) a. NUM N A DEM

otu nwaányị ọcha á
one woman white this
'This white-complexioned woman'

b. A N NUM DEM

ajọ nkjta abụọ ahụ
bad dog two that
'Those two bad dogs'

c. N A NUM DEM

akwụkwọ ọcha naáno ahụ
book white four that
'Those four white books'

d. N NUM A DEM

akwụkwọ ise ọcha ahụ
book five white that
'Those five white books'

The orders (31d. iii, iv and f. iii, iv) are attested in Igbo as (31) and (32) depict. One can deduce then that head-modifier order is not as fixed as the Principles and Parameters approach or the earlier minimalism of (1993, 1995) prescribe. However, it can still be accommodated within the core minimalist idea of feature-driven displacement though with slight modifications. What then are the possible explanations for modifier-shifts?

2.7 THE RUBINEAN THEORY OF MODIFIERS

Rubin (2002) sees modifiers as constituents of a functional category Modifier Phrase (ModP). Rubin proposes a theory parallel to the X-bar framework hypothesizing what he calls the Modifier Phrase Hypothesis, presented here as (33) and structured as in (34):

- (33) The Modifier Phrase Hypothesis: "...a substantive, empirically motivated theoretically beneficial functional category exists in the domain of modifiers..."

The Modifier hypothesis holds that there is a functional category which should be recognized as the modifier phrase which serves as the domain for modifying elements of the noun phrase. In his own words, he says: "this hypothesis claims that the head Mod forms a functional shell at the root of all modifiers, i.e. that it is the topmost functional head of their extended projections. This proposal replaces the standard assumption made perhaps merely by default, that modifiers, while unified as a notion, are nevertheless diverse in the nature of their structural form". (Rubin 2002). He exemplifies the hypothesis as being composed of the following kinds of elements in (34)

- (34) a) ... the very young child ... (AP)
b) ... the child playing checkers ... (VP)
c) ... the child under the table ... (PP)
 ... the debate at noon ... (PP)
d) ... these stone benches ... (NP)
e) ... the book that you are holding ... (CP)
 ... a movie to see ... (Inf)
f) I certainly will think about it. (AdvP or AP)
 He often reads that magazine. (AdvP or AP)
 John quickly learned Chinese. (AdvP or AP)
g) He left the stage shaking his head. (VP or SC)
h) They will meet each other in a restaurant. (PP)
 They will meet each other in an hour.
i) He left that day to seek his fortune. (NP)
j) I'll leave when John arrives. (CP)
k) ... unusually cold ... (AdvP or AP)

(cf. Rubin 2002)

All the underlined modifiers in (34), will now be structurally represented as in (35), with the variable lexical content of the modifier embedded as, or in, XP. This is in order considering its resemblance to other such proposals concerning functional categories in other domains, schematized in (35).

- (35) a. [IP I [XP ...]]
 b. [CP C [XP ...]]
 c. [DP D [XP ...]]
 d. [ModP Mod [XP ...]] Rubin (2002)

According to Rubin, the effect of such a claim on the architecture of the Minimalist Program is far-reaching. He adds that, it bridges the gap between a multiplicity of categories and that of having a cover term Mod representing; say, the adjective phrase, PP, CP, VP, or NP, when they serve as modifiers of a head. A tree diagram representation of the modifier hypothesis as it applies to the present work will look like (36).

Adopting a functional modifier phrase may provide a seeming solution to explaining some possible modifier-head shifts, but it does not in the real sense prove economical. For instance, the idea of economy in minimalism is called in question if more functional categories that have no real syntactic input to the derivation are allowed. Also, his idea of the Modifier Phrase being composed of various forms of expressions as given in (34) goes against the Uniformity Condition given above in (11). Moreover, since there is no modifier feature to be checked by moving the modifier to the edge of the phrase, and since derivation is supposed to be optimal, modifier movement is blocked by the

computational system, as such it cannot be correct. Consequently, we reject the Modifier Hypothesis for the slightly modified version of the feature-theoretic minimalist syntax.

2.8 HEADS AND MODIFIERS

Although there are controversies as to the proper definition of the term *head*, in recent years, the notion of 'head' has been extended from syntax into morphology. A number of positions taken by linguists of varying bents have in some ways complemented the term head.

In the studies of Chinese morphology, Huang (1982) argues that the assumption that natural language makes use of the concept of *lexical-headedness* in constructing complex morphological entities is untenable. There is no doubt that lexical headedness is real in natural language contrary to the observations of Huang (1982). We explore other positions.

In the field of computational linguistics, researches on the automatic semantic classification of Chinese compounds (Lua 1997; Chen 2000) all presuppose and verify the *endocentric* feature of compounds. In other words, they hold that compounds are composed of a *head* and a *modifier* and that the head determines the semantic category of the target, or the semantic category of the expression. The *head* then denotes that element of the phrase or expression that carries the more stable semantic content while the modifier is the element that adds additional information to it.

Again, studies in Principles and Parameters assume that endocentricity holds for every phrase in languages (Chomsky 1986a, Speas 1990, Haegemann 1991, and Chomsky 1995). Following the X-Bar Theory, specifiers and heads combine to

form referring expressions corresponding to the syntactic notion of a maximal projection. Modifiers refer to words or phrases that affect the meaning of another word, usually describing or restricting them. Lexical items and expressions may function as *specifiers*, *heads*, *modifiers*, or *complements* (Hawkins 1983:2). If the head of an expression describes a relation, one or more complements, or modifiers may be associated with the head (Hawkins 1983). The technical name for elements other than the head is *satellites*. Satellites of the head are in a way, as far as the nominal phrase structure is concerned, modifiers. The distributional possibilities of the modifiers within the domain of the head is the main concern of this work. Considering the observation that:

(37) Languages tend to place modifying elements either consistently before or consistently after modified elements (heads) Hawkins (1983:2).

It can be assumed that we are dealing with counter-examples to Hawkins' observation if we take into consideration that certain modifiers are in fact not fixed as to the position in which they occur with their heads. Can such an assumption make Igbo a head-last language? Certainly not! The issue is that we have to define the word *consistently* in (37) properly. If we take it to mean *all the time*, then Hawkins is wrong given the data in section 3.3.7; but if we take it to mean *most of the time*, then Hawkins is right. Without doubt, *all the time* is not feasible in any natural organism and language being an organic phenomenon cannot be different from other biological entities. That leaves us with the second option, *most of the time*. Given that languages place modifying elements *most of the time* before or after the head, how can we account for the times when placements do not follow the given pattern?

Another view of the head and modifier is that presented by Langacker (1987, 1991) reported in Ball (2003). According to Langacker (1987, 1991), the **head** is the profile determinant in a grammatical construction, particularly when it is the autonomous component in a construction showing notable A/D asymmetry; the autonomous profile determinant, A, is the head in such a construction, and the dependent component, D, is a **modifier**. Explaining further, we number as below:

- 38a. In a construction showing notable A/D asymmetry, and where the autonomous component, A, is the profile determinant, the dependent component, D, is a **modifier** of A (A is the **head**)
- 38b. In a construction showing notable A/D asymmetry, and where the dependent component D is the profile determinant, the autonomous component A is the **complement** of D.
- 38c. A basic distinction is drawn between **nominal** and **relational** expressions, depending on whether they profile a thing (abstractly defined) or a relationship.

The strength of the *autonomous profile determinant (A) cum dependent component (D)* definition of the head and its modifier is that their semantic attributes are particularly accounted for. Also it recognizes the bipolar roles of pronouns which have both specifier features and as well as a head. In other words, a pronoun could stand for a noun as is traditionally the case. But the problem with this definition is that the functional category specifier is not recognized. How then do we account for it; as complements or modifiers?

In answer to the question above, Ball (2003), building on the strengths of Langacker's analysis, brings together the X-bar notion of specifier as a functional category to have what he calls the bipolar theory of heads and modifiers. In his analysis, the functional category specifier is incorporated into Langacker's bridging the gap between a purely semantic analysis of Langacker and a purely syntactic analysis of X-bar to give a much more realistic definition of the head, modifier and complements. Following Langacker, Ball (2003) holds that heads are autonomous profile determinants, while modifiers are dependants and complements are never projecting items as such cannot be heads. He further avers that the specifier (determiners and auxiliaries) Chomsky 1970 (Remarks on Nominalizations) provide grounding predication for the heads. Ball (2003) explains as in (13).

According to Ball (2003), there are two poles, the referential and the semantic poles; and that adding the functional category of **specifier** as the determinant of the referential type of an expression leads to semantically better motivated

definitions of the **head**, **modifier** and **complement** functional categories which brings **syntax** into closer alignment with **morphology** and supports the notional definition of **parts of speech**. We cannot agree less with Ball here.

The **head** is the semantically most significant element of an expression whether it is autonomous or dependent (i.e. relational) (Ball 2003).

The definition above sees the head as the element that is the semantically most significant in a phrase. If we have an Igbo expression *mwoke ahu, that man*, a pro-DP hypothesis analysis will term it a DP as against the more notional interpretation as an NP used by Ball (2003). Given the definition above, that the head can be a dependent component, it follows that rejecting the DP hypothesis does not add any better explanation than if it is upheld, as such, we would retain the DP hypothesis in addition. Thus, on a relational or functional pole, the specifiers can head a phrase, but on a semantic pole it is open only to elements that can dominate the composite entity, as such, a pronoun can assume the position of an autonomous profile determinant (A) as well as that of the modifier – dependent component (D) as shown in figure (40).

The diagram (40) shows that the pronoun can be on the semantic as well as the relational pole given Ball's analysis. This may not be far from Abney's DP

hypothesis which recognises pronouns and determiners as heads of DP. If pronouns are specifiers as with determiners, then their heading the D projection is not ill-motivated.

Dixon (1992) examining *give*, *take* and *have* verbs in English avers that they take verbal complements which function as nouns, as such the head of a noun phrase is not necessarily a noun. His examples include:

He had a *look* (verb) at it
He took a *walk* (verb) around the park
She gave his nose a *tweak* (verb) (taken from Ball 2003)

In the sentences above, the italicized items which Dixon (1992) calls verbs function as nouns. By conversion, they are functional nouns and thus wellformed. The idea here is that any lexical item can function in any position in natural language.

Pullum, G. (1991) identifies gerunds and infinitive phrases as instances of noun phrases headed by clausal heads, e.g;

Going to the movies (gerund) is fun
Your *giving money to strangers* (gerund) is nice
That *you give money to strangers* (that complement) is nice
To go to the movies (infinitive phrase) is fun (from Ball 2003)

Pullum's identification of gerunds and infinitive phrases as instance of noun phrases headed with clausal heads does not in any way add to the notion of the noun as the head of a noun phrase. It only accounts for types of elements that can be in a noun phrase. However, difficulty arises as to the isolation of the head as a representation of a part of speech other than the idea of a nominal which they entail.

Another school of thought is the Langtech parser grammar. The head noun and its modifiers are seen as arbitrary representation of levels of relationships. Using

a kind of X-bar notation, it recognises two intermediate levels spelt out in terms of feature matrix [+X3L, -X3L, +Prehead, -Prehead]. The functional category D and Adjective are represented in the tree as positional levels in the internal structure of the noun phrase. The feature specification for Determiner and Adjective in the grammar will be something like

D is an abbreviation for [+X3L, -X2L, +PREHEAD, -POSTHEAD,..]

A is an abbreviation for [-X3L, +X2L, +PREHEAD, -POSTHEAD,..]

It claims that the X^0 level is the head of any category. The difference between this model and that of Ball (2003) is that while Ball (2003) has a semantic-based definition of the head, the Langtech parser grammar has a position-based definition of the head. In that regard, all elements are heads in their domain. This agrees with all generative models. While the pro-Langacker definition of heads concentrates on the autonomous profile determinants, this model does the same thing by arbitrarily using modifiers, Determiners, intensifiers, specifiers and adjectives as X3 heads but positionally distinguished from the head of the phrase containing them which also is an X^0 dominated by an X3. Note that 'X' is a variable that can represent N, D or A in the internal structure of the noun phrase, while 'L' is a term for the level at which the element positions in the whole structure. The pre- and posthead features are assumed to be similar to that of core principles and parameters approach.

Also in order to achieve a certain measure of generalization, the Grammar conflates the modifiers, D, A, and intensifiers. The term *Characterizer* (C) is used to designate all of them occurring at different levels. Take the phrase, the young English man, the tree structure will be as in (41).

The head of the phrase in (41) without doubt is the X^0 element *man* which has the same notation with the nominal modifier *English*. Considering economy principles of the Minimalist syntax, this grammar is over-generating intermediate structures, and as such should not be given a chance. Yet like its forbear, X-bar syntax, it observes that bar levels in a way, clearly present structures that could have been ambiguous without them. This, in the main, is the flaw of this approach since recent works on Generative Grammar eliminate x-bar for bare essentials (see 2.4.5).

From the views of headedness of Ball (2003) we see the unifying of semantic and syntactic definitions of the head which improves on Langacker's. And Lua's upholding of endocentricity in the field of computational linguistics is corroborated by the LangTech parsing grammar which defined the head in terms of their positions on the tree structure also advocating for a return to bar levels contrary to current views on phrase structures. We will assume a combination of the various definitions for our work here and define a three-pronged view of headedness. One, the head is a functional feature that determines the referential index of the phrase. Two, the head is the semantic element which all other

elements expand. Three, the head is the element which occupies a dominant position in the phrase copies as in the Igbo example *nwoke ɔmarịcha nke à*, this handsome tall man, below shows:

The dominant element that occupies the highest position in the Noun phrase domain is the N^0 *nwoke*. Also the Characteriser or the D element occupies the highest position in the modifier domain. In (42), the two nouns are both dominated by N2 which expands to N1 modified by N3. The numbering is a matter of notation. It is possible to have the same label for the two nouns. The difference between the (41) and (42) is that of the placement of the Characteriser or Specifier. While the Specifier in the English example is at the initial position of the phrase, it is at the end of the phrase in the Igbo example.

It is not possible to have a modifier occur after the Determiner as the example in (42b) shows. This implies that the DP hypothesis applies even in this language. No expansion or rearrangement can take place beyond the Determiner element in the noun phrase domain in the language. Let us assume then from (42b) that the modifier shift operations may not occur outside the nominal domain.

2.9 SUMMARY

In summary, given that head-modifier order may not be as fixed as the Principles and Parameters approach or the earlier minimalism of (1993, 1995) prescribe, and given Matushansky (2001) definition of the head as *a bundle of features*; and also given that Rubins *modifier hypothesis* does not specify the reason for movement; we hold that free occurring modifiers break no known principles of language and posit that a feature-theoretic explanation is a most optimal option. In other words, greed or ESI have roles to play in driving modifier shift in Igbo. As to the status of the head, holding a three-pronged view as we earlier advocated, will no longer suffice, hence, we postulate here that the leftmost constituent of the phrase heads the phrase; be it the semantic head or the modifier or the characterizer.

CHAPTER THREE

HEAD-MODIFIER STRUCTURES

3.0 INTRODUCTION

It is an established fact that many languages of the world have restrictions on the order between X^0 elements and their modifiers. The head of any category in languages has a canonical position in the phrase vis-à-vis its other ancillaries. The description of any category must conform to the typological structure of that language.

...the order between phrases representing subject, predicate and object (SVO) and between a modifier (A) and its head (N) are typological characteristics of languages". (Mats Eeg-Olofsson and Bengt Sigurd, 2001)

Also, leading concepts from the X^1 syntax infused into the Minimalist Program claim that there is a symmetrical relation between the various kinds of lexical items and the phrases they project. The checking domain consists of a head word its specifier(s) and its complements. This relation is said to be a universal grammar phenomenon. Thus, the structure of a word is likened to that of a sentence, whether simple, compound or complex. Following the generative conception of head-parameter requirements, on a superficial examination, one would assume that the Igbo head-modifier positioning negates parameter selection, but a closer examination proves that it does not. In this chapter, we analyse the various head-modifier patterns that are possible in the Igbo noun phrase. In order to determine the possible triggers for modifier shifts, we look at

two aspects of modifier-head relations; viz: distribution of modifiers vis-à-vis their heads and functional relations of modifiers to heads.

3.1 NOUN - MODIFIER PLACEMENT IN IGBO

In section 1.1, we noted that scholars have divergent views as to the Igbo nominal phrase structure regarding head-modifier placements or distributions. Anurudu (1999) proposes that cases of pre- and post- noun modification could be explained by appealing to features. These features he calls [+strong], [-strong], and [±strong]. His study claims that the strong featured modifiers pre- pose, the weak featured ones post- pose, while the ones having both features have the tendency to pre- or post- modify. The present study takes that work a step further and tries to find out what feature(s) is/are responsible for the modifier-head shifts - if really they are feature-dependent.

3.1.1 ADJECTIVES

Adjectives are considered as one of the main categories in Igbo (Uwalaka, 1997) heading the adjective phrase. There are five regular adjectives - *oma*, *ajọ/ajọọ*, *ocha*, *ukwu*, and *ojii*. Their major function in Igbo is to qualify the noun since they are always found within the noun phrase. (1) shows that they can only project within the noun domain.

- (1) a. Áda dī mmā/*oma
 Ada be goodness/ *good
 ‘Ada is good’
- b. Áda dī njọ/*ajọ
 Ada be badness/ *bad
 ‘Ada is bad’

c. Ada dij *ukwu

Ada be bigness

'Ada is good'

d. Ada dij ùcha/òcha /*òcha

Ada be whiteness *white

'Ada is white-complexioned'

The predicative use of adjectives in (1) fails possibly because the language does not permit adjectives being used as predicative items. All the derived nouns from the adjectives in (1) converge while the adjectives crash. The adjectives are derived from verbs and they in turn are stems for nominal adjectives as in (2).

(2) Adjective	Verb	Noun
Ocha 'white'	jcha 'to be white'	ùcha/òcha 'being fair complexioned'
Oma 'beautiful'	jma 'to be beautiful/fine'	mma 'being beautiful/fine'
Ojiĩ 'black'	iji 'to be black'	oji/nji 'being black'
Ajọ/ọjọọ 'bad/ugly'	ijọ 'to be ugly/bad'	njọ 'being bad'

(3) a. nwoke ocha	man white	'a fair complexioned man'
b. nwoke oma	man good	'a good/handsome man'
c. nwoke ojiĩ	man black	'a black man'
d. nwoke ojọọ	man bad	'a bad/ugly man'
e. nwoke ukwu	man big	'a big man'
f. ajọ mmadọ	bad person	'a wicked man'

The distribution of adjectives then is such that they are mostly post-nominal modifiers excepting *ajọ* which is pronominal, as shown in (3f). Mbah (1999)

identifies *ajo* as a noun which may well account for its pre-posing nature. Okwala (1997) also notes that tone is a major distinguishing feature of adjectives in the language. They all maintain a HH or HS tone. The claim of Okwala (1999), that *ajo* is a noun because it pre-poses a noun may be construed to be correct given that in a certain Orly dialect, *ajo* can be predicatively used as in

- (4) Nwaanyi ahụ gbara **ajo**.
 Woman that be (past) bad.
 'That woman is wicked'

This is the only case of a predicating adjective and could as well be a pointer to its pre-nominal occurrence. Again, '*ajo*' can be said to be a cognate nominal completing the meaning of the *-gba* holophrastic verb.

- (5) a. *gbàrà oma
 b. *gbàrà ukwu
 c. *chàrà ocha (with H tones)
 d. *jọrọ ojọọ

The argument, however, cannot be sustained based on this single evidence, in the face of other evidence to the contrary. *Ajo* is an adjective, though it shares morphological root with the nominal *njo*. Looking at it from a morphological angle, its derivation comes from the verb, *-jọ*, be bad as in (6).

- (6) *-jọ* → *jọrọ* 'be bad' (V) (stative)
Njọ 'badness' (N)
ojọọ 'bad' (adj) post-posing
ajo 'bad' (adj) pre-posing

From (6), we note that the difference between the two forms of *ajọ* as an adjective is the distribution in the nominal domain. Another evidence against the recognition of *ajọ* as a noun is its inability to occupy a focus position given that other nominals can.

- (7) **ajọ ka ọ bụ.*
 bad that s/he be

Example (7) fails to converge because focusing *ajọ* is not allowed since it is not a noun or a nominal. In the light of the fact that *ajọ* cannot minimally project, and it is a pre-modifying variant of the adjective, moreover because it cannot be focused, we conclude that it is not a noun but an adjective.

3.1.1.2 STACKING THE ADJECTIVE

Adjectives, unlike nouns, in Igbo cannot be stacked in a noun phrase.

- | | |
|---------------------------------------|-------------------------|
| (8) a. * <i>Ajọ ukwu nwoke</i> | bad big man |
| b. * <i>nwoke ọma ọcha</i> | man good white |
| c. * <i>nwoke ọma ojii ukwu</i> | man good black big |
| d. * <i>osisi ojii ọma ukwu ochie</i> | tree black good big old |
| e. * <i>osisi ọma ukwu ojii ochie</i> | tree good big black old |
| f. * <i>osisi ukwu ochie ojii ọma</i> | tree big old black good |
| (9) <i>Ajọ nwoke ukwu</i> | bad man big/great |

Emenanjo (1978) noted the four syntactic features of adjectives among which are consistent tone pattern even when associated with a noun, its non-predicative use which he calls inability to be used after the verb *di*, and its proximity to to the head of the noun phrase. One more feature we find here is its inability to be stacked. The failure of (8) and the convergence of (9) is explained by the

stacking restriction. (9) converges because there is an intervening noun between the adjectives.

3.1.1.3 ADJECTIVE: CONSTITUENCY AND AMBIGUITY

Siegel (1976) assumes nouns to be simple predicates of things, while adjectives are assigned some hidden semantic and/or grammatical complexity. In her *Double-Category* theory, Siegel proposes that the ambiguity in (10) and (11) reflects a fundamental dichotomy holding among adjectives in English. She suggests that there are actually two syntactically and semantically distinct classes of items conflated by the traditional category AP.

(10) a. Olga is a beautiful dancer

b. Olga is a dancer and she is beautiful.

c. Olga is beautiful as a dancer. / Olga dances beautifully.

(11) a. Jane is an intelligent student.

b. Jane is intelligent and she is a student

c. Jane is intelligent as a student... (Siegel 1976)

The first class is that of predicative. These occur as underlying predicates, although surface syntax may disguise this. Semantically, they are functions from entities to truth-values have meanings that can be extended. When they combine with a noun, the semantic result is predicate conjunction, which can be expressed through λ -abstraction. This is the source of the intersective (or ambiguous) reading in the examples (10) and (11).

Adjective modifiers in Igbo, on the other hand, present a similar intersective reading, but do not exhibit the predicative/non-predicative alternation noted for English. (12) has the same form and meaning as the English (10).

(12) a. *Ada bụ ògba egwu oma*

Ada is dancer dance good/beautiful

'Ada is a good dancer'

b. *Ada bụ ògba egwu oma*

Ada is dancer dance good/beautiful

Ada is a dancer of good music

c. *Ada bụ ògba egwu oma*

Ada is dancer dance good

'Ada is a dancer and she is beautiful'

The ambiguous reading of (12) could be linked to the constituency of the noun phrase which contains the adjective '*oma*'. Let us show with a phrase marker:

(13) a. [*ògba egwu*] *oma* 'a beautiful dancer'

b. [*ògba* [*egwu oma*]] 'a dancer of beautiful music'

The ambiguity stems from the constituent structure of the NP, *ògba egwu oma* and the fact that the adjective *oma* is a homonym for good, fine and beautiful. If we parse it as (13a), it will read unambiguously, *a beautiful dancer*; but if we parse it as in (13b), it will read differently as 'a dancer of good music'. Thus, the parsing determines the sense.

(13) c. *Igụ akwụkwọ dī oma.*

Reading book be goodness

'Reading is good.'

Adjectives from the examples given above are only attributives and never predicatives in Igbo. That explains why they occur in all cases as underlying nominal modifiers. Wherever they occur predicatively, they must be nominalized. This goes to strengthen Siegel's proposition that predicative

adjectives in English are underlying nominal attributive modifiers. Let us illustrate the structure thus:

(14) Noun-Adjective Structure

In Igbo, a head N is modified by an adjective post-nominally (3a-e) and pre-nominally as an exception to the rule (3f). It should be close to the noun or noun phrase it modifies.

A tree diagram representation of the adjective structure will be as figure 8a and b.

From the diagram above, the adjective is a minimal as well as a maximal projection within the nominal domain. From the diagram above, we note two possible distributions for the adjective though (fig. 8a) is the norm while (fig. 8b) is an exception. Thus, two structures are attested namely: Noun – Adjective and Adjective –Noun Constructions.

3.2 DETERMINERS

Following minimalist assumptions, the Determiner hypothesis entails those lexical items such as articles, pronouns, numerals and quantifiers which in many cases serve as nominal satellites are recognized as sub-sets of the functional category - determiners. All the sub-sets exist in Igbo save articles.

3.2.1 DEMONSTRATIVES

The status of the two demonstrative determiners in Igbo, *ahù* and *à*, are never in question. They are consistently post-nominal modifiers (Uwalaka 1997). They are similar to the English, *this/that* demonstrative. The only difference is that they have no plural counterparts as is the case in English. Plurality is derived from the noun it modifies. We illustrate their distribution in (15).

- (15) a. Nwoke *ahù/à* 'this/that man'
b. Onye *à/ahù* 'this/that person'
c. Nke *à/ahù* 'this/that one'
d. Ndi *à/ahù* 'these/those men'
e. Umụ-akā *à/ahù* 'these/those children'
f. **à/ahù* Ndi 'these/those men'
g. **à/ahù* Umụ-akā 'these/those children'

We see from (15) that the demonstrative determiners, *à* and *ahù*, do not possess the [+Plural] feature, hence they depend on that of the head noun. (15a) through (15c) have [+Singular] semantic feature are singular while (15d) and (15e) have [+Plural] semantic feature. We illustrate the demonstrative placement as (16).

- (16) Noun-Demonstrative Structure

In Igbo, a head N is modified by a demonstrative determiner always post-nominally (15a-c) and never pre-nominally (15f, g). It is the last element of the NP except where there is a relative clause as part of the NP.

The point here is that this set of nominal modifiers agrees with the head parameter selection for the language. That is, its distribution supports the post-head modifier placement whose structure will always be a Noun – Demonstrative structure. This, as well, conforms to the rule we posited earlier that the leftmost constituent of a phrase heads the phrase. This simply reduces the determiners to post-modifiers in the language. In a case where the determiner or adjective, or modifier precedes the noun it modifies, it simply assumes the head position as we see in (fig8).

3.2.2 NUMERALS

Another kind of lexical items that modify the noun is the category known as numeral. Numerals have over the years been classified as nouns, determiners or as syntactic heads. The traditional notion of the numeral is that of nouns that have number; the Minimalist Program sees it as a subset of the functional category - Determiner (D) (cf. Radford (1997).

3.2.2.1 SYNTACTIC NUMERALS

Ionin and Matushansky (2003), however, query the inclusion of the numeral in the determiner category and or its being taken as a syntactic head. On semantic grounds, they say, numerals should not be considered determiners or syntactic heads but modifiers derived in the syntax rather than the lexicon. They base their findings on the syntactic behaviour of certain numeral phrases which they call *multiplicative*, *subtractive* and *additive* numerals.

(17) Three hundred. (Multiplicative numeral)

(18) A hundred and three (additive numeral)

(cf. Ionin and Matushansky, 2003).

Thus (17) and (18), they opine, cannot be solely generated in the lexicon as single lexical items tagged numeral. This assertion is true to the extent that we consider only multiplicative, additive, and subtractive numerals (19), but it will not be completely true if we consider other single item numerals.

(19) Three hundred less one. (Subtractive numeral)

It does not give a picture of the whole numeral class. All numerals are not syntactically generated just as all nouns are not derived nouns. (17) through (19) are just aspects of the lexical items classified as numerals, as such, we cannot generalize, based on the above evidence, that numerals are syntactic derivands from the computational system.

Numerals are as much heads as they are modifiers of the noun just as we observed for adjectives, above since they represent a distinct class of lexical items in the language. The additive, multiplicative, or subtractive numeral though syntactically generated can only occur as one single figure when written in figures. Also numerals have definitive feature [count] which marks it out as a determiner.

(20) a. Mmadu iri na abuo additive numeral

Person ten and two

'Twelve persons'

b. Mmadu iri anọ multiplicative numeral

Person ten four

- 'Forty persons'
- c. Mmadụ nàrì ábụọ multiplicative numeral
 person hundred two
 'Two hundred persons'
- d. Mmadụ iri ábụọ nà àtọ multiplicative additive"
 Person ten two and three
 'Twenty three persons'
- e. Puku mmadụ ábụọ multiplicative
 Thousand person two
 'Two thousand persons'

In (20), we see that the numeral is both lexical and syntactic. What go for additive and multiplicative numerals in Igbo, (20a) and (20b), in English, are single lexical numerals, twelve and forty respectively, while (20c) through (20e) are multiplicative numerals.

- (21) a. *Otù onyē* lexical
 'One person'
- b. *Ábụọ ká m chọrọ* lexical
 Two that I want
 'I want two'
- c. *ọgụ mmadụ* lexical
 'Twenty persons'
- d. *nnụ mmadụ* lexical
 'four hundred persons'
- e. *nnụkwuru nnụ* lexical/syntactic

Four hundred-upon four hundred

'Many four hundreds/ many or innumerable'

f. *nny-nny* additive

four hundred, four hundred

'eight hundred'

(21a-d) are lexical numerals while (21e-f) is a syntactic numeral. The form of (21e) shows a verb-like morphological derivation where *-kwuru*, a bound morpheme is affixed to the root, *nny* before being modified by another *thny* giving a meaning of many or innumerable. Thus, the syntactic or lexical classification of numerals is not an issue, but fixing the referential and deictic role of numerals. Whether we take a numeral item like one, two, three, etc., which are singly generated in the lexicon, or we consider the multiplicative, additive, or subtractive numerals which are syntactically derived, one thing is sure about all numerals – they are definitive of nouns. They define the semantic feature [count] which nouns possess. Numerals specify, or better-still modify nouns. The numerals represent a grammatical class of lexical items that specify number, as such, whether syntactic or lexical, are heads in their own respects just as pronouns are. We therefore overlook the lexical/syntactic distinction of Ionin and Matushansky (2004) for a more economical determiner hypothesis reported in Radford (1997) which sees numeral as a subclass of the determiner category.

3.2.2.2 CARDINALS

The ordinal realization of numerals in Igbo is determined, in the main, by tone. Cardinals retain their inherent tone pattern while the associative tone rule applies to ordinals.

(22) a.	Otù onyè	'One person'
b.	Mmadụ ànọ	'four persons'
c.	Mmadụ iri	'ten persons'
c.	Nàri mmadụ	'hundred persons'
d.	Puku mmadụ	'one thousand persons'
e.	Ndè mmadụ	'one million persons'
f.	Ijèri mmadụ	'one billion persons'

The cardinal numerals in (22) show pre- and post-nominal modifying distribution. *Otu*, *nari puku*, *nde*, and *ijèri*, all show a pre-nominal distribution while *ànọ*, *iri* and most numeral modifiers in the language are post modifiers.

3.2.2.3 ORDINALS

The realization of ordinals in Igbo has hitherto been analysed as being determined by tone alone (Emenanjo 1978:54; Uwalaka 1997).

(23)a.	Ụlọ àtọ	house three	'three houses'	cardinal
b.	Ụzọ ànọ	way four	'four ways'	cardinal
c.	Akwà ise	cloth five	'five clothes'	cardinal
(24)a.	Ụlọ ātọ	house three	'third house'	ordinal
b.	Ụzọ ānọ	way four	'fourth way'	ordinal
c.	Akwā īse	cloth five	'fifth cloth'	ordinal

Note that the elements in (23) retain their inherent tones but the application of the associative tone rule in (23) examples generate the ordinals in (24). This

analysis is correct. However, we discover that ordinals can be lexically determined in combination with tones. The distinction between cardinal and ordinal numerals is lexically done between *otù*, one, and *mbu*, first. *Mbu* is the only lexical ordinal. Any noun it modifies, regardless of the tone must be ordinal. See this in (25).

(25)a.	Nwa mbu	child first	'first child'	ordinal
	b. μ mu mbu	children first	'first children'	ordinal
	c. Ndj mbu	people first	'the first people'	ordinal
	d. Onye mbu	person first	'the first person'	ordinal
	e. Nke mbu	one first	'the first'	ordinal

Even if the inherent tone of *mbu* (LH) is retained, the phrases above cannot be anything other than ordinals. Now consider the following data.

(26)	a.	Nwa abuq	child two	'the second child'	ordinal
		c. Nwa atq	child three	'third child'	ordinal
		d. Otù nwa	one child	'one child'	cardinal
(27)	a.	μ mu àbuq	children two	'two children'	cardinal
		b. μ mu àtq	children three	'three children'	cardinal
		c. μ mu ànq	children four	'four children'	cardinal
(28)	a.	Ndj abuq	people two	'the second people'	ordinal
		c. Ndj atq	people three	'the third people'	ordinal
(29)	a.	Onye abuq	person two	'the second person'	ordinal
		b. Onyē atq	person three	'the third person'	ordinal
(30)	a.	Nke abuq	one two	'the second'	ordinal
		b. Nke atq	one three	'the third'	ordinal

In (26a and b), we see that *nwa*, a definitive term, when modified with numerals other than *otu* which is a cardinal counterpart of *mbu*, gives an ordinal reading; whereas *umu* in (27), an indefinite term compared to *nwa*, gives cardinal readings. (28 through 30) all give ordinal readings with or without associative tones. Why is this the case? Let us say it is because of the semantics of the words themselves. Ordinals are definitive and exclusive numerals. They separate from the pack. Since *nwa*, separates from *umu*; *onye* specifies person, *ndi* a given set, and *nke*, a particular thing, it follows that by superiority condition tone is irrelevant here to the ordinal reading of the phrases. To this end, we conclude that ordinals in Igbo can also be determined by the inherent nature of the nouns apart from tone. We illustrate then, the numeral structure as in (31):

(31) Noun-Numeral Structure

In Igbo, a head N is modified by a Numeral postnominally (20a-e) and in some cases prenominally (21a, c, and d).

3.2.3 QUANTIFIERS

Just like the numeral, the quantifier forms another class of functional lexical items that is a sub-class of the determiner as Radford (1997) reports. According to Emenanjo (1978:72), there are three quantifiers in the language namely; *niile*, *all*, *dum*, *all*, and *naabo*, *two*. Uba-Mgbemena (2006) identifies more than three quantifiers to include; *otutu*, *many*, *ufodu*, *some*, and *olenōle*, *a few*. Other quantifiers include *imirikiti*, *many*, *oberē*, *little*, *òkàrà*, *half*, and *òbulà*, *any/ every*.

3.2.3.1 NUMERAL QUANTIFIERS

Igbo has a number of quantifiers that are derived from numerals. They range from *àbụọ* (two) to *iri nà itoolū* (nineteen) with the exception of nine.

<i>Naābọ</i>	'twosome'	derived from	<i>àbụọ</i>	'two'
<i>Naāto</i>	'threesome'	" "	<i>àto</i>	'three'
<i>Naāno</i>	'foursome'	" "	<i>àno</i>	'four'
<i>Neēse</i>	'five-some'	" "	<i>ise</i>	'five'
<i>Neēsii</i>	'six-some'	" "	<i>isii</i>	'six'
<i>Naāsaà</i>	'seven-some'	" "	<i>àsaà</i>	'seven'
<i>Naāsato</i>	'eight-some'	" "	<i>àsato</i>	'eight'
<i>Neēri</i>	'ten-some'	" "	<i>iri</i>	'ten'
<i>Neēri nà otù</i>	'eleven-some'	" "	<i>iri nà otù</i>	'eleven'
<i>Neēri nà àbụọ</i>	'twelve-some'	" "	<i>iri nà àbụọ</i>	'twelve'
<i>Neēri nà àto</i>	'thirteen-some'	" "	<i>iri nà àto</i>	'thirteen'
<i>Neēri nà àno</i>	'fourteen-some'	" "	<i>iri nà àno</i>	'fourteen'
<i>Neēri nà ise</i>	'fifteen-some'	" "	<i>iri nà ise</i>	'fifteen'
<i>Neēri nà isii</i>	'sixteen-some'	" "	<i>iri nà isii</i>	'sixteen'
<i>Neēri iri nà àsaà</i>	'seventeen-some'	" "	<i>iri nà àsaà</i>	'seventeen'
<i>Neēri nà àsato</i>	'eighteen-some'	" "	<i>iri nà àsato</i>	'eighteen'
<i>Neēri nà itoolū</i>	'nineteen-some'	" "	<i>iri nà itoolū</i>	'nineteen'

Numeral quantifiers are all post nominal modifiers and cannot be shifted nor stand alone without their nominal head.

- (32) a. *Ha naābọ* 'both of them'
 b. *Ha naāto* 'three of them'
 c. *Ụmù naāsaà* 'seven of you'

d. *Mmady neēri nà otù* 'eleven persons'

e. **wèta naābọ*

f. **wèta naāto*

g. **wèta neēri nà otù*

h. **wèta neēri nà ásato*

(32a through d) are well-formed. They are used as post modifiers of the head. In (32d), the quantifier effect vanishes in the translation of *mmady neēri nà otù*; giving rise to what looks like an ordinary numeral *iri nà otù* (eleven). This is because the distinction between quantified and non-quantified numeral is made insignificant when nouns are modified with numeral quantifiers but there is a consistent meaning when pronouns are modified with numeral quantifiers as in (32a, b and c). However, the meaning change does not affect their status as numeral quantifiers in Igbo. The other examples in (32e through h) are ill-formed because numeral quantifiers must be with their noun head.

3.2.3.2 QUANTIFIER PLACEMENTS

The quantifying determiners, when modifying the noun, are also grouped into post modifiers, obligatory premodifiers and optional premodifiers. Quantifiers generally are postmodifiers but pre and optional premodifiers are products of modifier shifts.

(33) a.i. *Mmady niilē*

Person all

"everyone"

b. i.

* *niilē mmady*

a. ii. *Mmady dum*

Person all

b.ii.

* *dum mmady*

			"everyone"
a.iii.	ihe ɔbɔlɑ	b.iii.	* ɔbɔlɑ ihe
	Thing any		
	"anything"		
a. iv.	Imirikiti mmadu	b.iv.	?mmadu imirikiti
	A lot person		
	"a lot of people"		
a. v.	Ọtutu mmadu	b.v.	?mmadu ọtutu
	Many person		
	"Many persons"		
a. vi.	Mmadu ɔfodu	b.vi.	ɔfodu mmadu
	Person some		
	"some people"		
a.vii.	Ihe obere	b.vii	obere ihe
	Thing smallness		
	"a small thing"		
a.viii.	Mmadu ọlemoole	b.viii	ọlemoole mmadu
	Person fewness		
	"a few persons"		

The examples in (33i-iii) are post-modifying quantifiers; (33iv, v) are obligatory pre-modifiers, while (33vi-viii) are optional pre-modifiers. Note that the last two sets are shifted modifiers. The numeral quantifiers listed above and exemplified in (32) are consistently post-modifiers. The quantifier distribution can then be illustrated as in (34):

(34) Noun-Quantifier Structure

In Igbo, a head N is modified by a quantifier post-nominally (33i-iii), obligatorily pre-nominal (33iv, v) and in some cases optionally prenominal (33vi-viii).

NOUN-NOUN MODIFIERS

The noun-noun construction is one of the ways of generating new nouns and modifying head nouns in Igbo. In the absence of a rich inflectional morphology, Igbo and most members of the Benue-Congo group of languages in general employ the association of nouns to achieve grammatical purposes. Since the literature is replete with works on the noun-noun construction in Igbo, Yoruba and other Benue-Congo languages, we are not going to duplicate them here, but will analyse them based on their distributions in the maximal noun projection.

3.3.1 GENITIVE MODIFIERS

There is no distinction between alienable and inalienable possession in the language and the genitive feature is both structurally and tonally realized. Structurally, the noun having the genitive feature is always N2, and tonally, the genitive or possessive noun always has a down-stepped tone at the juncture of the two nouns.

(35)	a. akwụkwọ Āda	book PN	'Ada's book'
	b. ugbọ Ōbi	vehicle PN	'Obi's vehicle'
	c. ụmụ Kānu	children PN	'Kanu's children'
	d. ụlọ Ōbi	House PN	'Obi's house'
	e. Aka Āda	Hand PN	'Ada's hand'
	f. *Āda akwụkwọ		

Figure 3.

From the examples in (35a-e), we note that the first syllable of the second noun has a downstepped tone required for the marking of genitive feature. We use the superscript T to signify the tone of the genitive noun. Gen.P represents a possible functional phrase Genitive category headed by the abstract T, which can be classified as a sub-class of the noun phrase. We illustrate as in (36):

(36) Noun-Genitive structure

In Igbo, a head N is modified by a genitive noun in post-head position (35a-e), never in a pre-head position (33f) and is tonally distinguished from other noun modifiers.

3.3.2 ASSOCIATIVE MODIFIERS

While the genitive nouns refer to proper nouns, the associative nouns are common nouns associated with other common nouns to show a *kind of* relation. The first noun is assumed to be the head while the second noun modifies the first. The noun-noun construction, otherwise called the associative construction, is one of the ways of modifying the head in a language that does not have much inflection.

3.3.3 THE ASSOCIATIVE TONE

Igbo simple nouns are classified into five groups using their inherent tone patterns as the basis. The patterns credited to Green and Igwe (1963) is reproduced here for expository purposes.

(37)	Class I	HH	e.g.	isi,	oke,	aka,
				'head'	'male',	'hand'
	Class II	LH	e.g.	òke,	iri,	àkwa
				'rat'	'ten',	'egg'
	Class III	HL	e.g.	obi,	ezé,	ulò
				'heart',	'king',	'house'
	Class IV	LL	e.g.	áfè,	ùgò,	ùdù
				'shirt'	'eagle',	'pot'
	Class V	HS	e.g.	egò,	ugbò,	mmā
				'money',	'farm',	'beauty'

Example (37) shows the tonal groupings of Igbo two syllable nouns. Tone as a modifier changes the inherent tonal patterns of two merging words in an associative construction. We look at the changing patterns in (38).

- (38)
- a. HHH + HH become HH HS e.g. isi-okwū 'main point'
 - b. LH + HH become LH HS e.g. Ògbu agwọ 'snake killer'
 - c. LL + HH become LL HS e.g. Àgbá ewū 'goat's jaw'
 - d. HS + HH become HHH HS e.g. Ego akī 'kernel money'
 - e. HS + LH become HH SS e.g. Ezi ādā 'a good daughter'

The question one may ask here is why the tonal patterns have to change when merged with other words. Goldsmith (1980) traces the reason to the existence of

what he calls 'the obligatory contour principle', which holds that co-occurring HH syllables necessarily change form to avoid similar occurrences.

Hyman (1985), however, sees the downstepped H syllable not as a case of lowering but downdrift. In fact Nwachukwu (1996) sees the tone variation as a product of downdrift just like Hyman sees it. He advocates a tone marking convention that does not recognize the downstepped tone due to the fact that downstepping does not exist independent of a preceding H tone. Thus the syllables of the word *akwukwọ* would sound like (39) where each preceding H is on a higher pitch level than the one following it.

(39) H
 H
 H
 A- kwu - kwọ

It is established that there is a melodic rhythm of downdrift in Igbo, hence it is most appropriate to limit it to the discourse or sentential level. However, downdrift is a product of an initial Low tone triggering the lowering of subsequent High tones. In other words, (39) is not a true representation of downdrift since there is no Low tone to trigger tone lowering.

3.3.4 IRREGULAR ASSOCIATIVES

The irregular associatives are so called because they have idiomatic reading other than a *kind of* reading.

- (40) a. *aka mgbèdè*
 Hand evening
 'Towards evening'
- b. *ụwà mgbèdè*
 world evening

'Late achievers'

c. anụ ọhia

meat bush

'wild animal / a fool'

d. Ime ọkwá

pregnancy guinea fowl

'Illegitimate pregnancy'

The relationship between N1 and N2 is more of a comparison and figurative use of language than a *kind of* relation. In (41a) the body part 'hand' is used to signify direction towards evening or the setting of the sun. The examples in (41b, c, and d) compare the evening to a late achiever, the wildness of a wild animal to that of a fool who is not tamed to reason, or the indiscretion of the guinea fowl to having no definite mate to that of a young woman having illegitimate pregnancy. All the same, the glosses in (41a-d) give a semblance of a head-first structure, so we classify them with the N + Modifier pattern.

3.3.5 REGULAR ASSOCIATIVES

The association of one noun to another is said to be regular if the meanings of the words separately are intact in the noun-noun structure. The regular N-N phrases form the most productive class of noun-nouns in Igbo just as Owolabi (1976) reports for Yoruba. Consider the data in (41).

(41) a. Akwụkwọ békéè

Book English

'English book'

b. akwụkwọ nrí

leaf food

- 'edible leaf / vegetable'
- c. *ugbo* Naijiria
Motor Nigeria
'Nigerian car'
- d. *ulo enwe*
house monkey
'a cage or house for monkey'
- e. *ihe uwa*
thing world
'worldly thing'
- f. *agha Iraaki*
war Iraq
'Iraqi war'
- g. *olu uzu*
work road
'road work'
- h. *isi iyi*
head spring
'a spring source'

All the data in (41a-h) show a *kind of* relation between N1 and N2. Unlike (40) which have denotative as well as figurative readings for the two nouns, the nouns involved in (41) retain their separate readings. The (N2s) are consistently modifiers. That is, N2 describes N1, delimiting it.

3.3.7 SHIFTED MODIFIERS

The modifiers can, in fact, premodify or post-modify their heads.

- (43) a *nwoke ogologo* b. *Ogologo mwokē.*
Man length length man
'a tall man' 'a very tall man'
- (44)a *nwoke ɔmarjcha* b. *ɔmarjcha nwoke*
Man handsomeness handsomness man
'a handsome man' 'a very handsome man/ handsomeness of man'
- (45)a. *nwoke mkp̄umkp̄u* b. *mkp̄umkp̄u nwoke*
Man shortness shortness man
'a short man' 'a very short man/shortness of man'

Presenting them in a sentence form will be as in the examples below.

- (46) a *Òbi bụ nwoke ogologo.*
Obi is man length
'Obi is a tall man.'
- b. *Òbi bụ Ogologo mwokē.*
Obi is length man.
'Obi is a very tall man.'

The examples in (46) show all the possible readings of the Noun-noun phrase *nwoke ogologo*. (46a) is the normal structure having the modifier of the noun after the noun, while (46b) is the derived form having the meaning of (46a) and an additional *intensive* feature.

Other examples of modifier shift are listed below.

- (47) a *Anyị chọrọ ego kịrịkịrị*
we want(-rv) money coins
'We want coins'

- b. Anyị chọrọ kịrịkịrị egò
 1pl want(-rv) coins money
 'We want coins (much smaller coins)'
- (48) a. Q bụ nwoke mkpụmkpụ.
 3S be man shortness
 'He is a short man.'
- b. Q bụ mkpụmkpụ nwoke
 shortness Man he 3S be
 'He is a very short man.'
- (49) a. Mmādu nnukwu bjàrà ebe à taà.
 Person plenty come(-rv) place this today
 'Many people came here today'
- b. Nnukwu mmādu bjàrà ebe à taà.
 Person plenty come(-rv) place this today
 'So many people came here today'
- (50) a. I bụ nwa ntàkịrị.
 2S be child smallness
 'You are a small child'
- b. I bụ ntàkịrị nwa.
 2S be smallness child
 'You are a very small child'
- (51) a. Òbi bụ nwoke ọmarịcha.
 PN be man handsome
 'Obi is a handsome man.'
- b. Òbi bụ ọmarịcha nwoke.
 PN be handsome man

- 'Obi is a very handsome man.'
- (52) a M nwèrè oche oberē.
 1S have (-rv) seat smallness
 'I have a small seat'
- b. M nwèrè obere ochē
 1S have (-rv) smallness seat
 'I have a very small seat'
- (53) a I bụ mmāḍụ ochiè.
 Person oldness that 2S be
 'You are an old person'
- b. I bụ ochiè mmāḍụ.
 2S be oldness person
 'You are a very old person' (a very experienced person)
- (54) a O yì akwà nkarj̄nka.
 3S wear clothes oldness
 'S/he wears old clothes'
- b. O yì nkarj̄nka akwà.
 3S wear clothes oldness
 'S/he wears the old clothes'
- (55) a Nye m efere mbadamba.
 Give 1S plate roundness
 'Give me a round plate'
- b. Nye m mbadamba efere.
 Give 1S plate roundness
 'Give me the very round plate'

- (56) a. ?Ada bụ mwaànyị ezigbō.
 Ada is woman best of
 'Ada is a very good woman'
- b. Àda bụ ezigbo mwaànyị.
 Ada is woman best of
 'Ada is a very good woman.'

Considering that (47b) implies both (47a) and an additional intensive reading, and same can be said of all the examples (48) through (55), it follows that there is a grammatical purpose served by modifier shift. Note that the obligatory premodifier or shifted modifier *ezigbo* in (56) is not so acceptable when used post-head as in (56a). This is because it is an obligatory premodifier. Although, what functions as an obligatory premodifier in a dialect of Igbo like Ngwa, may in the standard dialect be optional as is the case with *mbadamba*, *mkpunkpu*, *obosara* (Oluikpe 1979:67).

We shall argue that there are features that drive modifier shift. However, such features cannot be visible morphologically else there would be morphological difference between the base modifiers (unmoved ones in post-head position) and the shifted ones. In (43) through (45), the modifiers *ogologo*, *omaricha* and *mkpunkpu* shifted to a pre-head position obtaining an *intensive* or *grade* features. The same is true of all the obligatory pre-nominal modifiers in (42) for they have *absoluteness* or *extremeness* features. Let's assume for now that modifier shift satisfies the requirements for grade and extremeness features of nouns which may not be fully satisfied in situ. We can hypothesize as (57)

- (57) Modifier shift satisfies the grade and/ or extremeness features.

A noun that semantically includes the notion of measure and gradability when post modifying remains the normal grade but when shifted obtains an aggravation or intensification of the feature in terms of size, quality, or measure. This could also be viewed in terms of definiteness and indefiniteness features.

We observe that there is a distinction for *grade* seen in terms of the modifier position in the notional continuum made visible by its pre-head placement. The intensive or extremeness grade feature of the shifted modifiers manifest when they are shifted, else they remain at a mean kind of grade. Note that *ogologo mwoke* can read as (58a) and or (58b)

- (58) a. 'a very tall man'
b. 'the tallness of a man'

whereas *mwoke ogologo* only reads 'a tall man.' Also nouns that denote extremeness like, best, complete, exclusive etc. tend to premodify. See (42) given here as in (59):

- (59) a. Ezi, 'best, essence of'
b. Ezigbo 'essence, original, the best'
c. Oke 'male/high'
d. Qmarjcha 'very beautify/handsome/nice'

In (59) we see that all the nouns have inherent extremeness or grade feature which makes them to pre-pose. Except (59d) which optionally shifts, though it is more often used in a shifted position, all the rest are obligatorily prenominal modifiers as shown in (42). We can say, then, that modifiers with inherent extremeness or having intensive meaning obligatorily prepose while shifted modifiers acquire extremeness or intensification when shifted. But if so, why can't every noun shift and obtain a grade feature? Note that inherent features are

only semantically present but are not morphologically visible. Only certain kinds of nouns have such features.

3.4 MODIFIER RELATIONS TO HEADS

The associative modifiers, as we have noticed in this study, can be grouped into different functional or relational classes. The functional relationship between the head and its modifier could be that of subject and its complement, agent-patient, source, instrument, but shifting is determined by the inherent feature of each modifier.

3.4.1 APPOSITIVE MODIFIERS

These are modifiers where N1 is same as N2.

- | | |
|--------------------------|--------------------------------|
| (60) a.i. Nwaányi ákwuná | b. i. Nwaányi bú ákwuná |
| Woman prostitute | woman be prostitute Im.pron. |
| 'a prostitute' | 'A woman that is a prostitute' |
| ii. Nwa nwoke | b. iii. Nwa bú nwoke |
| child man | child be man |
| 'a male child' | 'A child that is male' |
| iii. Mmadu ófèkè | b. iv. mmadu á bú ófèkè |
| Person fool | person this be fool |
| 'a foolish person' | 'this person is a fool' |

The examples in (60a and b) the relationship between N1 and N2 is an appositive relationship. That is, N2 can stand alone in place of N1.

3.4.2 CONSTITUTE MODIFIERS

The modifiers in this group specify the constitution of the head N. N1 is made of N2.

(61) a.i. Itè igwè pot iron 'a steel pot'	b. i. Itè èjiri igwè mee pot Im.pron. use (rv) iron make 'a pot made of steel'
a.ii. Itè ụrọ pot clay 'a clay pot'	b. ii. Itè è jiri ụrọ mee pot Im.pron. use(rv) clay make 'a pot made of clay'
a.iii. Òpì igwè Horn steel 'A steel flute'	b. iii. òpì è jiri igwè mee horn Im.pron. use(rv) clay make 'a flute made of steel'
iv. òpì àchàrà Horn steel 'A bamboo flute'	b. iv. òpì è jiri àchàrà mee horn Im.pron. use(rv) clay make 'a flute made of bamboo wood'
v. àkwà osisi bed wood/tree 'A wooden bed'	b. v. àkwà è jiri osisi mee bed Im.pron. use(rv) clay make 'a bed made of wood'

The N-N phrases in (61a i-v) are derived from their (61b) counterparts. Although the N2s still specify a *kind of* relation to N1s, it is such relation of N1 being made of N2.

3.4.3 INSTRUMENT HEADS

The relationship between a head and its modifier could be that of *instrument* and its modifiers. The examples below depict that.

- | | |
|------------------|--------------------------------|
| (62)a.i. Mbu ɥlɔ | b. i. ihe bu ɥlɔ |
| Carrier house | thing (rel.T) carry house |
| 'pillar' | 'a thing that carries a house' |
| ii. Ntɥ egbè | b. ii. ntu eji agba egbe |
| Ashes gun | ashes used shoot gun |
| 'gun powder' | "ashes for shooting" |
| iii. Ngwu jī | b. iii. ihe eji egwu jī |
| Digger yam | thing used to dig yam |
| 'yam digger' | "tool for digging yam" |
| iv. Mmà ekwū | b. iv. mmà na-adj n'òsekwū. |
| Knife kitchen | knife be -being in kitchen |
| 'kitchen knife' | "knife used in the kitchen" |

In (62a), note that nouns with the instrumental reading are the heads (N1) while the modifiers are the N2s. The instrument-modifier relation in the (b) examples is like the relation between subjects and complements in 3.1. There is no possibility of modifier shift.

3.4.4 MANNER MODIFIERS

Manner can be represented in the associative construction as a modifier type as the examples in (65) show.

- | | |
|-------------------------|-----------------------------------|
| (63)a.i. <i>Ọrụ akā</i> | b. i. <i>ọrụ eji aka arụ</i> |
| Work hand | work used hand working |
| 'hand work' | "work done with hands" |
| ii. <i>Ije nwaayọọ</i> | b. ii. <i>ijè anà-èje nwaayọọ</i> |
| Walk slowness | walk one be waling slowness |
| 'a slow walk' | "a movement done slowly" |
| iii. <i>ọlụ ike</i> | b. iii. <i>ọlụ siri ike</i> |
| work hardness | work be rv strength |
| 'hard work' | "work that is hard" |
| iv. <i>ọnwụ ikē</i> | b. iv. <i>ọnwụ mere n'ike</i> |
| death hardness | death happen(rv) in strength |
| 'sudden death' | 'death that happened suddenly' |

The N2 in the N-N phrases in (63a) are all instances of modifiers that depict manner while the (b) examples show their place in a sentence form. It is not possible for manner modifiers to pre-pose in relation to their heads.

3.4.5 REASON MODIFIERS

The modifier can relate to the head as its reason as in the examples below.

- | | |
|-------------------------|-------------------------------|
| (64)a.i. <i>ọsọ egō</i> | b.i. <i>igba ọsọ mākà egō</i> |
| race money | run race for money |
| 'a race for money' | 'to run for the money' |

ii. akwa agụụ	b. ii	akwa màkà agụụ
cry hunger		cry for hunger
'the cry because of hunger'		'a cry for hunger'
iii. mgbidi mgbòchi	b. iii	mgbidi màkà mgbòchi
wall barring		wall for covering
'partition wall'		'wall for partition'

All N2 are reasons for the existence of N1s in the (64a) examples. The alternative examples in (b) are not sentences but extended phrases of (a) examples.

3.4.6 LOCATION MODIFIERS

N1s in this group are located in terms of N2s, i.e., N1 is located in N2 as (65) shows.

(65)	a.i.	Òke ụlọ	b.i	Òke à bi n'ụlọ
		rat house		rat this lives in house
		'a house rat'		'this rat lives in the house'
	ii.	Òke ọhịa	ii.	Òke à bi n'ọhịa
		rat bush		rat this lives in bush
		'a bush rat'		'this rat lives in the bush'
	iii.	Ụlọ ìkpà	iii.	ụlọ à dj n'ìkpà
		house wilderness		house this be in wilderness
		'a house in the wilderness'		'this house is in the wilderness'

All the post modifiers in the examples in (65i-iii) are locative modifiers.

3.4.7 QUALITY MODIFIERS

Modifiers can specify an abstract quality which the head of the two nouns has as in the examples below.

(66)a. i	Akwà ọhụụ	b.i.	akwa à dī ọhụụ
	Cloth newness		cloth this be newness
	'a new cloth'		'This cloth is new.'
ii.	Nwoke ọmarịcha	ii.	nwoke à dī/bụ *ọmarịcha
	Man handsome/fine		
	'a handsome man'		
iii.	Oke ehī	iii.	ehī à bụ oke.
	Male cow		cow this be male
	'a male cow'		'this cow is male'
iv.	Ezi mmadụ	iv.	mmadụ à bụ *ezi
	Essence person		
	'a very good person'		
v.	Ezigbo ọgwụ	v.	ọgwụ à bụ *ezigbo
	Essence/original medicine		
	'an original medicine'		

Note that in (66i-iii), the modifying quality is the N2, as usual, but in (66iv-vi) the modifying noun is the N1. Also (66iii, v, and vi) bars predicative use of their modifiers. The pre-posing modifiers are instances of modifiers that obligatorily prepose as we have seen in section 3.3.

3.4.8 COLOUR MODIFIERS

The modifiers in this class present qualities that can be verified in terms of colour, hence we call them colour modifiers.

- | | | | |
|------|------------------------|------|-------------------------------|
| (67) | a.i. Qla èdò | b.i. | Qla à dī èdò |
| | Ring yellowness | | ring this yellowness |
| | 'gold / a yellow ring' | | 'gold / this ring is yellow' |
| | ii. Qla òcha | ii. | Qla à dī òcha |
| | Ring whiteness | | ring this whiteness |
| | 'gold / a white ring' | | 'silver / this ring is white' |
| | iii. Akwà ojī | iii. | Akwà à dī ojī |
| | cloth blackness | | cloth this be blackness |
| | 'a black cloth' | | 'this cloth is black' |

All the modifiers in (67i-iii) depict colour. The N1s are modified by the N2s and using a stative verb-be *dī*, in the sentences in the (b) examples, they all can be termed complements of their heads.

3.4.9 MEASURE MODIFIERS

The modifiers depicted in this group are modifiers that have measurable or gradable qualities such as length, size, height, or dimension.

- | | | | |
|----------|------------------|------|--------------------|
| (68)a.i. | Nwoke ogologo | b.i. | nwoke à dī ogologo |
| | Man length | | man this be length |
| | 'a tall man' | | 'this man is tall' |
| | ii. Oke mmadụ | ii. | *mmadụ à dī oke. |
| | Great person | | |
| | 'a great person' | | |

iii. Nwoke mkpụmkpụ Man shortness 'a short man'	iii. nwoke à dī mkpụmkpụ man this be shortness 'this man is short'
iv. Ihe ntàkịrị Thing smallness 'a small thing'	iv. ihe à dī ntàkịrị thing this be smallness 'this thing is small'
v. efere mbadamba round roundness 'a round plate'	v. efere à dī mbadamba plate this be roundness 'this plate is roundish'

The examples in (68i, iii-v) show various measure nouns used as post modifiers in the (a) examples and as complements in the (b) examples while (69ii) obligatorily premodifies. Also we note that it is possible to optionally prepose the modifiers in (68) with the exception of (68ii).

3.4.10 QUANTIFYING MODIFIERS

The quantifying determiners, when modifying the noun, are also grouped into post-modifiers, obligatory premodifiers and optional premodifiers.

(69) a.i. Mmadụ niilē Person all "everyone"	b.i. * niilē mmadụ
ii. Mmadụ dum Person all "everyone"	bii. * dum mmadụ
iii. Ihe ọbụlā Thing any "anything"	iii. * ọbụlā ihe

iv. Ìmirikiti mmadu	iv. mmadu imirikiti
A lot person	
"a lot of people"	
v. Òtutu mmadu	v. mmadu otutu
Many person	
"Many persons"	
vi. Mmadu ufodu	vi. ufodu mmadu
Person some	
"some people"	
vii. Ihe obere	vii. obere ihe
Thing smallness	
"a small thing"	
viii. Mmadu olemoole	viii. olemoole mmadu
Person fewness	
"a few persons"	

The examples in (69i-iii) are post modifying quantifiers while (69iv-viii) are optional premodifiers.

3.4.11 SOURCE MODIFIER

This group of nouns specify source of the head noun. N2 is the source of N1.

See (70).

(70)	a.i. Mmanya ngwò	i. mmanya siri na ngwò pùta
	Wine rafia palm	wine from(rv) in rafia palm go come
	'Rafia palm wine'	"wine got from rafia palm tree"

ii. Mmanya nkwo	ii. mmanya siri na nkwo puta
Wine palm tree	wine from(rv) in palm tree go come
'palm wine'	"wine got from palm tree"
iii. Mmiri iyi	iii. mmiri siri n'iyi yiputa
Water spring	water from(rv) spring spring out
'spring water'	"water that gushes from a spring"
iv. Mmiri omi	iv. mmiri di na omi.
Water well	water be in well
'well water'	"water from a well"
v. Mmanu anu	v. Mmanu nke anu meputara
Oil bee	oil which bee made
'honey'	"Oil from bee"
vi. Mmiri okporo igwe	vi. mmiri ne-eru n'okporo igwe
Water pipe steel	water be- flowing in pipe iron
'Pipe-borne water'	"water flowing from iron pipe."
vii. Abu nnonu	vii. abu nnonu na-abu.
Song bird	song bird be-singing
'bird song'	"song made by bird"

(71i-vii) are all instances of source modifiers. The N2s are sources from which N1s are produced. Note also that source modifiers cannot be shifted. From the section above, we notice that modifier shift is possible only with modifiers that specify measurable qualities or quantities. See this in (72) through (81).

- (72)a. Onye olī
Person stealing
'a thief'
- b. **ohi onye* (complement)
- (73) a. itè igwè
pot iron
'a steel pot'
- b. **igwè itè* (make)
- (74)a. Mbu ulò
Carrier house
'pillar'
- b. **ulò mbu* (instrument)
- (75)a. Ijè nwaayọọ
Walk slowness
'a slow walk'
- b. **nwaayọọ ijè* (manner)
- (76)a. ọsọ egō
race money
'a race for money'
- b. **ego ọsọ* (reason)
- (77)a. Òke ulò
rat house
'a house rat'
- b. **ulò òke* (location)
- (78)a. Ọla ọcha
Ring whiteness
'gold / a white ring'
- b. **ọcha ọla* (colour)
- (79)a.i. Ezi mmadụ
Essence person
'a very good person'
- b.i. **mmadụ ezi* (quality)

ii. Nwoke ɔmarjcha	ii. ɔmarjcha nwoke (quality)
Man handsome/fine	handsome/fine man
'a handsome man'	'a very handsome man'
(80)a.i. Nwoke ogologo	b.i. ogologo nwoke (measure)
Man tallness	tallness man
'a tall man'	'a very tall man/ the man's tallness'
ii. Nwoke mkpũmkpũ	ii. nwoke à dij mkpũmkpũ
Man shortness	man this be shortness
'a short man'	'this man is short'
(81)a.i. Mmadũ niilē	b.i. * niilē mmadũ (quantifying)
Person all	
"everyone"	
ii. Mmadũ dum	b.ii. * dum mmadũ ..
Person all	
"everyone"	
iii. Mmadũ imirikiti	b.iii. Ìmirikiti mmadũ ..
A lot person	
"a lot of people"	
iv. Mmadũ ufõdũ	b.iv. ufõdũ mmadũ ..
Person some	
"some people"	

Thus, *complement, appositive, make, instrument, manner, reason, location, colour,* and *source* modifiers cannot shift while *quality, measure* and *quantifying* modifiers may. Putting the three together, let us assume that we have *measure* and *grade* as respective cover terms for *quantity* or *quality*. Let us

assume also that both terms can be measured or graded. So (72) through (78) cannot be shifted since none of the modifiers there has measure or gradable features.

However, (78) fails in spite of the fact that colour can be measured. The explanation to that may be that the language does not grade colour since a colour say *ũcha*, may be interpreted as whiteness or fair-complexion or there may be other devices for measuring colour. (79i) represents a high grade that obligatorily shifts while (79ii) is the optional grade that may shift.

(81i and ii) represent what is called in logic as universal quantifiers (Kahane 1973:90). Their measure is generally taken to be equal to zero. Hence *dum* and *niile* are not logically speaking measurable. However, the other quantifiers represent what in logic is called existential quantifiers. They have existential import reducible to at least one. Thus, (81iii and iv) are measurable and can be shifted. If the assumptions above are correct, it follows that modifier shift in Igbo seeks to categorize modifiers in terms of levels in a gradable progression or measure. Thus, a modifier may shift to the left edge of the head noun to obtain grade (includes measure) feature. One consequence of that is that the shifted element becomes the head of the new structure. We assume also that no trace is left when modifiers shift. Traces are erased since the higher modifier is a copy of the lower.

3.5 STRUCTURING GRADE MODIFIERS

The account given above is fraught with problems viewed in the light of X-bar schema. If the modifier shifts or moves, to what node does it move and what happens to its trace? The Minimalist framework dispenses with phrase structure for a bare phrase one. The bare phrase structure builds a tree using only *Merge* and *Copy*.

- a) Select the lexical items you want to use to build your sentence. They will be bundles of phonological and syntactic (semantic) features (This initial list is called the *Numeration*).

Numeration: {/àsa/ /àda /, /akwà ya /, /nà/ }

- b) Stick two of them together to create a constituent, an unordered pair. (This operation is called *Merge*. Some features or requirements of the two bundles involved may be checked or satisfied when merged).

{/àsa/, / akwà ya / }

- c) Give the constituent a label by copying and merging one of the pairs of the set with the set itself, to create a new set, consisting of the labelling element plus the old set. (This is the operation by which the head "projects" a phrase.

- d) We now have a complex constituent which is ready to be merged with another constituent: either another straightforward bundle plucked from the Numeration, another complex element created in another workspace

(e.g. a PP adjunct phrase like *n'èzi*, *outside*), or else by Copying an element you've already got in your tree and Merging the copy with its own tree. Let us think of movement in this form.

e) Let's merge first */nà /*, and then see what we have:

$\{/àsa/, \{/àsa/, /akwa ya / \} \} + \{/nà / \} = \{/nà /, \{/àsa/, \{/àsa/, /akwa ya / \} \} \}$

and then we label this set with whichever constituent we want to project, in this case

$\{nà\}$: $\{/nà /, \{/nà /, \{/àsa/, \{/àsa/, /akwa ya / \} \} \}$

/Infl/ */verbal/* */noun/*

A tree diagram of that will be like:

Now, assume */Ada/* has some Case features, being an NP, which needs to get checked. */àsa/*, the verb cannot check them, because it is a participle. However, */nà/* being the inflectional category has got nominative case features to check. If we make a copy of */àda/* and merge it with its own tree, then it will be able to check its Case features against the features of */nà/*. By the way, we take for granted that the subject internal hypothesis (see Radford 1997, pp. 315) is applied in the generation of the subject here.

Copy: */àda/*, the internal argument of the verb */àsa/*.

From the derivation outlined above, we are able to generate an acceptable Igbo sentence with only Merge and copy. Correspondingly, we can generate the head-modifier-shift data in Igbo using only Merge and Copy, the difference being that there is no Case feature to be checked but as we have earlier hinted, there are grade features to be checked. Call it a kind of category conflation achieved through shifting.

Assume a numeration with fully formed binary phrases having nouns modified with grade or measure lexical items.

{/nwoke/, /ogologo/}

Merge the numeration above to derive a constituent then give the constituent a label by copying and merging one of the pairs of the set with the set itself, to create a new set.

We now have a complex constituent ready to be merged with another item or a copy of the modifying lexical item. To generate the grade featured noun phrase, copy the modifier /ogologo/ and merge it with the label of the head. This will be like the numeration below.

{/nwoke /, {/nwoke/, /ogologo/}} = {/ogologo/, /nwoke /, {/nwoke/, /ogologo/}}

We label the new structure as /ogologo/ and that gives an intensive measure reading. Thus, *ogologo* becomes the head of the phrase.

Note that the source of the copy is in surface derivation erased. This is represented by the strikethrough line it has in situ and its index. The same process is replicated for all the gradable, measure and quantifying modifiers as shown below:

From the examples given, we can safely say that the bare phrase structure accounts better for the shifted modifiers than the X-bar theoretic one. The question of trace is also taken care of by the copy/erasure explanation of the modifiers. What then are the consequences of the bare phrase Structure? Harley (2002) outlined some consequences of the bare phrase structure, thus:

- a. No need for PS-rules, even ones as abstract as an X-bar schema.
- b. Phrase vs. head status of a given element is determined by the derivation:
 - a phrase is any element that is not dominated by a copy of itself
 - a head is any element that does not dominate a copy of itself
- c. Something like /Ada/ (84), as represented above, will be both a phrase and a head
- d. C-command can be treated derivationally: it's the relationship between an element and whatever it is merged with.

- e. The requirement that 'moved' elements c-command/govern their traces need not be stated independently: if Move is Copy plus Merge, and if c-command is just Merge, then the 'base' position of a Moved element has to be c-commanded by the Moved position...
- f. Movement must obey cyclicity. That is, you cannot merge inside anything you've already built. Merge is just concatenation plus projection. (Harley 2002).

(b) above is circular and cannot be sustained. A head is both a minimal and a maximal projection and as such must dominate a copy of itself. Following (c-f) we see that the examples in (85 through 92) have both head and phrase statuses, are rightly governed or c-commanded and obey cyclicity. The only difference is that their application is to clausal constituents and not to noun phrases as we have done here. We shall characterize the structure as in (93).

(93) Modifier – Noun – Modifier structure

In Igbo, a head N can be modified prenominally, and/or post-nominally.

The inherent features of the modifier determine the position.

When the inherent feature of the modifier determines its position in the nominal domain through Merge or move, as the case may be, the modifier position in the right side of the head is completely erased since it does not affect the Determiner as we can see here in (94).

From (94) we observe that the Characteriser/D remains in situ being one of the modifying elements of the noun head *nwoke*. Applying modifier shift to the datum above will only operate within N2 giving us *nwoke omaricha* or *omaricha nwoke* in which case the shift does not affect the D element. The implication of this then is that the leftmost constituent of the structure is the structural head of the Noun phrase. This assumption solves the problem of double structures as we presented in page 78 for the Noun-adjective structure.

Instead of representing (95b) as an NP, following our argument above, the structure should be straightforwardly labelled AdjP as in (96) below.

That brings us to revise (93) thus:

(97) Head – Modifier structures

In Igbo, a head element is always the leftmost constituent of the noun phrase domain.

Thus the inherent features of the modifier which cause them to shift not only check the feature but do so by assuming the headship of the phrase. In other words, those features can be called edge features.

3.6 SUMMARY

This chapter has discussed forms of modifier-head placements in the Igbo noun phrase with particular emphasis on the shifted modifiers, accounting for features triggering modifier shift. It is held in this study that grade and measurability are inherent features of the modifiers that shift. The restriction of this phenomenon to nouns and nominals with measure or grade features shows that such movement is feature-driven. The (im)possibility of finding other kind of nouns modifier-shifting shows that the grade feature is perhaps an indication that they are as suggested here.

In conclusion, we posit that shifting in the case of head-modifier relations is triggered by what we call *inherent grade* features of modifiers seen as edge feature. And lastly, we conclude that the Igbo nominal phrase structure, obeys

the binary parameter selection of UG on the argument that pre-modifiers are feature-determined being a last resort option and that the premodifiers are in fact converted heads. This leaves parameter selection intact.

In the next chapter, we look at other forms of modifiers such as the *mà* verb complements, the subject/object switch, exceptives, duplicatives, and conjunctives with regard to their modifier placements.

CHAPTER FOUR

OTHER FORMS OF SHIFTS

INTRODUCTION

In the previous chapter, we looked at data involving some forms of head-modifier shifts. We realise there are other forms of shifts that are not purely cases of modifier shifts. We consider data from the verb, '*jma*', *to know* which permits shifting of its complement constituents. Also we analyze subject/object switching (Uwalaka, 1988), and other forms of modifiers such as the exceptives, duplicatives, conjunctives and pronominal Goal/theme switch in double object structures.

4.1 *JMA* VERB COMPLEMENTS

The verb '*jma*', 'to know', in Igbo allows the shifting of its infinitive and participial complements to pre-head positions. Its verb complement shift is such that the meaning of the two expressions remains unaffected, though not without some thematic undertone. Defining the process as movement may seem unmotivated; as such, we analyze its main features whether feature-driven or not (Chomsky, 1993; Lasnik, 1995).

- (1) a. Q marala [*igba ïgwè*].
3sg know-perf. to ride iron
'S/he has known how to ride a bicycle'
- b. Q marala [*igwe ïgba*].
3sg know-perf. iron to ride
'S/he has known how to ride a bicycle'

c. Q marala [igba ïgwe].
 3sg know-perf. to ride iron
 'S/he has known how to ride a bicycle'

d. Q marala [ïgwe āgba].
 3sg know-perf. iron riding
 'S/he has known how to ride a bicycle'

(2) a. Āda mā [èsi [ōfe òwèrè]].
 Ada know to cook soup Owerri
 'Ada knows how to cook Owerri so

b. Āda mā [ōfe òwèrè] èsi].
 Ada knows soup owerri to cook
 'Ada knows how to cook Owerri soup'

(3) a. Āda chọọ [isi [ōfe òwèrè]].
 Ada want-rv to cook soup Owerri
 'Ada would have cooked Owerri soup'

b. * Āda chọọ [ōfe òwèrè] isi / èsi].

The infinitive complement of the skill verb, *mā*, in (1a) is shifted in (1b). Same is represented in (1c) and (1d) replacing the infinitive complement (henceforth InfP) with the participial complement. (2a) and (b) also have the same effect. The inclusion of aspect feature in (1) does not impede the shifting of the nominal complement. (3a) converges while (3b) crashes just as expected, for only the verb *jma* allows this kind of movement. Eze (1997) noticed that cognitive verbs do not allow complement shift except the verb *jma*. He did not

explain why the verb allows such shift. He, however, holds the view that a direct movement without first nominalizing the InfP complement fails to converge. On account of personal communication with native speakers from various Igbo speaking areas, we discover that nominalizing (i.e., participial nominal) before complement shift is optional. Complement shift can occur in both cases.

- (4) a. *Q marala igba igwe*
3sg know-perf. to ride iron
'S/he has known how to ride a bicycle'
- b. *Q marala igwe igba*
3sg know-perf. iron to ride
'S/he has known how to ride a bicycle'
- (5) a. *Ada mà esi/isi ofe Owerri*
Ada know cooking/to cook soup Owerri
'Ada knows how to cook Owerri soup'
- b. *Ada mà ofe òwèrè isi/esì.*
Ada know soup owerri cooking/to cook
'Ada knows how to cook Owerri soup'

From the examples above, we see that complement shift is possible whether the InfP is nominalized or not. Virtually all verb types that denote activity, whether physical or mental, can complement the *ima* verb but those without activity such as; occurrence, quality, and equative verbs cannot. What then are the identifiable features for complement shift?

If we equate it with the noun-noun modifier shift phenomenon earlier identified in chapter 3, then, every shifted complement of the *imā* verb is a nominalized

verb phrase, making it equal to a noun-noun construct, having the nominalized verb as head and the cognate object as modifier. If we say that some grade or measure features are checked in the shifted position as we have said for the noun-noun types, then there should be some visible gradable feature evident, at least, in the interpretation. But we don't see any grade feature at all. What is noteworthy is that in all cases of the *jma* complement switch the reading is "skilled, or expert." But the *skill, know-how or expertise* is not a feature of the complement but that of the verb *jma*. In other words, the movement occurs within the domain of the verb *jma* as in (6).

(6) a.

b.

As we can see from the diagrams (6a and b), it is the verb that licenses the shift of the complements when they are in its governing domain but if they are removed from the domain of the verb, swapping would be prohibited as shown in (7).

Although the *imà* complement at the base of the structure in (7) is shifted and converges, it is not so when moved out of the verbs governing category. When moved, it must retain its normal structure which is infinitival plus its object else it crashes. This presupposes that there must be a difference between Movement operation and shifting operation. Shifting occurs within the given category and does not leave that domain. From this we conclude that complement shifting is an idiosyncratic feature of the verb *imà*, *to know*, in Igbo.

4.2 SUBJECT/COMPLEMENT SHIFT

Uwalaka (1988) was the first to observe the phenomenon shift between subjects and the complements which she called subject/object switching in Igbo. We present below some of her data to that effect.

- (8) a. Ada wèrè iwe
 Ada be(past) anger
 'Ada was angry'

- b. Iwe wèrè Ada
 anger be(past) Ada
 'Ada was angry'
- (9) a. Ada gbajiri aka
 Ada break(past) hand
 'Ada broke her hand'
- b. Aka gbajiri Ada
 hand break(past) Ada
 'Ada broke her hand'
- (10) a. Ada bàrà mamìrì
 Ada pass(past) urine
 'Ada urinated (involuntarily)'
- b. Mamìrì bàrà Ada
 Urine pass(past) Ada
 'Ada urinated (involuntarily)'
- (11) a. Ada kwàrà ùkwàrà
 Ada cough (past) cough
 'Ada coughed'
- b. Ùkwàrà kwàrà Ada
 Cough cough(past) Ada
 'Ada coughed.'
- (12) a. Ada rìsìgà imì
 Ada drop-bits-be nose
 'Ada has a runny nose'

b. Imi r̄isigà Ada

nose drop-bits-be Ada

'Ada has a runny nose'

(13) a. Ada gburu nma n'aka

Ada cut(past) knife prep.hand

'Ada cut herself on the hand'

b. Nma gburu Ada n'aka

Knife cut(past) Ada prep. hand.

'Ada was cut on the hand with knife'

(14) a. Ada kp̄r̄ȳ isi

Ada cover (past) blindness

'Ada is blind'

b. Ìsì kp̄r̄ȳ Ada

blindness cover(past) Ada

'Ada is blind'

(15)a. Ada t̄r̄ȳ egwù

Ada be(past) fear

'Ada was afraid'

b. Egwù t̄r̄ȳ Ada.

Fear be(past) Ada

'Ada was afraid'

(16) a. Ohia gbara ok̄ȳ.

Bush be(past) fire

'The bush burnt'

- b. Ọkụ gbara ọhia.
 fire be(past) bush
 'Fire burnt the bush'

- (17) a. Ada riàrà orià
 Ada sick(past) sickness
 'Ada was sick'

- b. Orià rjàrà Ada
 Sickness sick (past) Ada
 'Ada was sick'

From the data above, we notice that the ICs in the (a) cases are not thematic objects but form part of the lexical requirements of their containing verbs. They constitute what Uwalaka (1982, 1988) calls the V-N complexes. The Ns, are not arguments of the verb but are parts of the lexical requirements of the verbs. Inherent complements, as they are called, could be preverbal or post-verbal depending on the semantics of the verb. For instance all the verbs involved in the shifting phenomenon form a single phrase; verbal.

- (18) wèrè iwe → X_[the cause] wèrè y_[patient] iwe
 Be-rv anger
 'was angry'

- (19) tūrū egwù → X_[the cause] tūrū y_[patient] egwù
 Be-rv fear
 'was afraid'

- (20) riàrà orià → X_[the cause] riàrà y_[patient] orià
 be-rv sickness
 'was sick'

In (18) through (20) as well as all other cases given above, the two constituents of the verbs swap as long as there is no specific cause of the experience suffered by the so-called subject. The real subject position is unfilled. In other words, this is not a case of subject/object but that of complement shift which rightly fits into our explanation about head-modifier shift in Chapter Three that shifting items must be members of the same unique class. Without a visible subject, modifier-shift is possible since the two items are internal elements of the verb. The notion of a subject/object switch becomes misleading since the two swapping elements are deeply rooted as kinds of complements being verb-internal elements. A tree diagrams representation would be like the ones below:

The diagrams in (21a, b and c) show the positions of the nominal elements within the verb phrase. One can safely conclude that there is nothing like a subject/object swap since there is no subject in the phrases above. With this point clarified, we can succinctly say that shifting in the cases above happens within a phrasal category. The complements are parts and parcel of their containing verbs.

- (22) Okwu ahụ wèrè Ada iwe
 Talk that _[cause] angered Ada _[affected] anger _[complement N]
 'The statement annoyed Ada'

The *affected* items suffer the actions denoted by the verb phrase. Note that the *affected* items are not affected by the verbs alone but with their inherent complements. If we assume the existence of a causative subject, we will have something like (22). What (22) connotes is that the two nominal elements in the subject/IC shifting phenomenon are verb internal elements. The subject of (18a), no doubt from (21) and (22) is the affected entity in the projection and occupies the internal position as regards verb argument relation. We say then that there is only one affected argument in the sentence which satisfies the affected role and there is no direct object involved.

However, (23) seems to contradict what we have said concerning (18-20) in that the subject can be interpreted as fulfilling causative and affected roles at the same time. This is where non-volition comes into play. Uwalaka (1988) noted that all cases of swapping of roles have the semantic feature of not being voluntary actions. Let us characterize as in (23) and (24).

(23) Ada gbùrù nmà n'aka

NP_[non volitional cause] [affected]_i cut t_i knife_[instrument] on hand

'Ada cut herself on the hand'

(24) Ada gbùrù onwe-ya nmà n'aka

PN_i [non volitional cause] cut refl.pron_i. knife_[instrument] on the hand

'Ada cut herself on the hand'

Ada in (23) doubles as the *involuntary cause* of the action denoted by the verb as well as the *affected* given that no normal person will intentionally afflict injury on his or herself; (although thugs and 'hooligans can do it as a show of manliness). This observation agrees with Uwalaka's (1988) assertion that swapping verbs carry an unintentional or involuntary index.

The reflexive pronoun in (24) co-refers to its antecedent and as such carries the same thematic role- the affected role. The trace in (23) also co-refers with its antecedent. In other words, just as Ada and iwe in (22) are internal elements of the verb; so are the involuntary subjects and their reflexives or traces as the case may be. Also, a verb like *màrà mmà*, to stab, cannot be shifted due to the fact that it can never be construed to have a non-volitive argument.

(25)a. Òbì màrà onwe-ya nmà n'afọ

PN_[volitional cause] stab (past) refl.pron. knife _[instrument] on the stomach

'Obi stabbed himself on the stomach'

b. *Nmà màrà Obi n'afọ.

Certainly (25) further strengthens the argument for non-volitive reading of swapping verbs. (25b) fails to converge because; the subject *nmà* cannot perform the action denoted by the verb *màrà* which presupposes a voluntary human subject. On the other hand, non-volition may not be the only reason for shifting as in (26) and (27).

(26) Obi dára adàh

NP fall(past) fall(cognate N)

'Obi fell (down)'.
b. *Adàh dára Ada

(27) Oyi nàtụ M.

Cold be-hit 1sg.

'I am feeling cold'.
b. *M nàtụ oyi.

(26) through (27) suggest that principles, other than the semantic feature of non-volition, are responsible for objects swapping in Igbo. If volition is all it takes, there is no reason why (26b and 27b) cannot converge since the verbs depict non-volitive semantic readings just like the shifted cases above. I am not, however, inferring that all verbs allow shifting, certainly not. The issue is that volition is not the only reason for permutable verbs. There must be other factor(s) responsible for the phenomenon. What then informs subject/object switching if we say that non-volition cannot be the reason for shifting in the

instances given above? Given the semantic features of the verbs that allow shifting, one can infer reasons for such.

Semantic features of verbs that allow shifting are all linked to experience verbs. The overriding feature is that of non-volition translatable to Uwalaka's deep semantic cases of [-intent], [-cause], and [-controller]. The other features include [+affected] and [+animate] features.

"Verb: Experiencer [-intent] [-cause], [-controller], [+affected], [+animate]"

There are three positive valued features, namely: experiencer, affected, and animate. These features account for the behaviour of the verbs. An experiencer has an experience and he is the affected of the action of the verb. The diagram (28) shows the representation of bundle of features of such verbs while (29) represents features and structure.

(28)

(29a)

Since the subject slot is empty, any of the complements could shift to fill that position. In (29a), the experiencer shifts while in (29b), the IC shifts.

(29b)

From the diagrams above, there is no inherent [cause], [intent] or [controller] of the experience experienced by the experiencer. As a result, that aspect is left empty, at least in the computational system. Observe (30) and (31).

(30) Iwe wèrè Ada

Anger (IC) annoy (past) Ada (affected)

'Ada was annoyed.'

(31) Orià (IC) rjàrà Ada

sickness sick(past) Ada

'It made Ada sick.'

The *Cause* is not given. What this comes up to is that the symmetrical or shifting verbs have unfilled subject positions since shifting is not possible where there is a clear-cut external argument of the verb as the defective shifted cases in (32) through (34) depict.

(32) a. O mèruru Àda àhu

Pron. spoil(past) PN body(cognate N)

'S/he/It wounded Ada'.

b. *O àhu mèruru Àda

c. * O Àda mèruru àhu

(33) *Obi mèrurɔ Àda àhɔ.*

PN spoil(past) PN body(cognate N)

'Obi wounded Ada',

b. **Obi Àda mèrurɔ Àda àhɔ*

c. **Obi àhɔ mèrurɔ Àda*

(34) *Àda mèrurɔ àhɔ.*

PN spoil (past) PN body (IC)

'Obi wounded Ada',

b. *àhɔ mèrurɔ Àda*

The failure of the examples in (32b,c) and (33b,c) and the convergence of (34a and b) show that switching is clearly not possible when spec IP_i is filled. This position, perhaps, best explains the syntax of switching verbs. It agrees with Lasnik (1995) which sees such movements as EPP motivated.

Let us assume that any of the nominal elements may move to the unfilled pre-verb subject position for the purposes of focusing a given theme since they are both object items. That sounds plausible given that no two expressions are exactly the same. If the verb *ima*, to know, as we have seen above has such feature that allows its complements to shift within its domain. We argue then here that some verbs designated by the switching or shifting complements are same as the *ima* kind of verb but with a different purpose. And just as the modifier-shift conveys incremental effect on the noun, so does the switching of complements confer incremental or thematic effect on whichever complement precedes. This obviously is not Greed-motivated but ESI-motivated, since shifting is optional.

In conclusion, subject/complement shifting is one of the cases of syntax-semantics interactions that make language not just a structured, organized contraption used by man but a meaningful purposeful means of expressing situations, relations and things. There are, in effect, two kinds of shift identified so far- modifier-shifting, and complement-shifting. They both operate within a phrasal domain and not a sentential domain! The modifier shift occurs within a nominal or noun phrase domain and the *jma* complement switch within the *jma* verb domain and the subject-complement shift also within a verb domain.

4.3 EXCEPTIVE MODIFIERS

Although Uba-Mgbemena (2006:54) classified *soosọ* and *so*, *obuladi* and *tumadi* as adverbs of degree/proportion, and Emenanjo (1978:168) calls *naānj* and *soosọ* clausal modifiers, we will use the term *exceptive* modifiers to designate them. We call them *exceptives* considering their semantic input in sentences. They behave like the kind of English lexical items that Quirk et al. (1985) call *limiters*. They include:

<i>Naānj</i>	'only'
<i>Soosọ</i>	'only'
<i>So</i>	'only'
<i>Bèere(so)</i>	'except'
<i>Tumadi</i>	'especially'
<i>Obuladi</i>	'not even'

Five issues are noted of the six exceptives; namely, some of them are post-modifiers, some pre-modifiers, some can pre- and post-modify, some allow intervening lexical items between them and their heads; and they may modify, nouns, pronouns, nominals or complementizers.

EXCEPTIVES IN POST-HEAD POSITION

The post-head position can be occupied by two of the exceptives, *naānj* and *soṣṣo*. Let us see this in (35).

(35)a. *Āda naānj mà ihe m nà-ème.*

PN Only know thing 1sg be-doing

'Only Ada knows what I am doing'

(b) *Āda soṣṣo mà ihe m nà-ème.*

PN only know thing 1sg be-doing

'Ada alone knows what I am doing'

(c) **Āda sọ mà ihe m nà-ème.*

(d) **E nwēla chí ọzọ Chukwu bèere.sọ.*

(e) **Umụ gị dị ike Òbì tùmàdì*

(f) **Nepà e nyeghị anyị ọkụ otu ụbọchị ọbuladi*

Nepa imp. give-neg 1pl fire not even one day

'NEPA did not give us power, not even for one day.'

From the data above, *naānj* and *soṣṣo* are the only postmodifying exceptives.

However, they can as well be premodifiers.

4.3.1 EXCEPTIVES IN PRE-HEAD POSITION

The following are exceptives occupying the pre-head position.

(36)a. *Naānj Āda mà ihe m nà-ème.*

Only PN know thing 1sg be-doing

'Only Ada knows what I am doing'

(b) *Soṣṣo Āda mà ihe m nà-ème.*

only PN know thing 1sg be-doing

'Ada alone knows what I am doing'

(c) *Sọ* Àda mà ihe m ná-ème.

only PN know thing 1sg be-doing

'Ada alone knows what I am doing'

(d) *E nwela chí ọzọ bèeresọ* Chukwu.

Im(pron). Have-neg. god another except God'

'Have no other god except God'

(e) *umụ gị dị ike tumàdị* Òbì .

children 2sg be power especially Obi

'Your children are strong especially Obi.'

f) *NEPA e nyeghị anyị ọkụ ọbuladị* otu ụbọchị

NEPA imp. give-neg 1pl fire not even one day

'NEPA did not give us power not even for one day.'

In (36), we see that all of them can pre-modify nouns; *naānj* and *soosọ* inclusive. There are other combinatorial possibilities.

4.3.2 COMBINATORIAL POSSIBILITIES OF EXCEPTIVES

Three exceptives, *naānj*, *soosọ* and *sọ* can co-occur in given order. While *naānj* and *soosọ* allow intervening items between them and the head, *sọ* allows only if the co-occurring exceptive is not *soosọ*. We show that in the table below.

Table 1. Combinatorial Possibilities of *naānj*, *soosọ* and *sọ* with nouns

Exceptives	Preceding	Middle	Intervening head noun	Last
<i>Naānj</i>	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
<i>Soosọ</i>	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
<i>Sọ</i>	Yes	No	Yes	No

Table 1 shows that *naānj* and *soosọ* can occur in any position while *sọ* occurs only in pre-head position. Consider (37).

- (37)a *naānj soqsɔ* Ada only, only Ada 'Ada alone'
 soqsɔ naānj Ada " "
- b. *naānj* Ada *soqsɔ* only, only Ada 'Ada alone'
 soqsɔ Ada *naānj* " "
- c. *sɔ naānj soqsɔ* Ada only, only, only Ada 'Ada alone'
 sɔ soqsɔ naānj Ada
- d. *sɔ* { *naānj* Ada *soqsɔ* } only, only Ada 'Ada alone'
 { *soqsɔ* Ada *naānj* }
- e. *sɔ* Ada { *naānj* } only, Ada only 'Ada alone'
 { *soqsɔ* }
- f. *naānj* { *sɔ* Ada } only, Ada only 'Ada alone'
 { **soqsɔ* }
- g. **sɔ* Ada { *naānj soqsɔ* }
 { *soqsɔ naānj* }
- h. * { *naānj soqsɔ* } Ada *sɔ*
 { *soqsɔ naānj* } Ada *sɔ*
- i. **naānj* { Ada *sɔ soqsɔ* }
 { Ada *soqsɔ sɔ* }
- j. **naānj* { *sɔ soqsɔ* Ada }
 { *soqsɔ sɔ* Ada }

We observe that *naānj* and *soqsɔ* can occur in any position to the noun both in combinatorial and single modifying structure (37a-f). But *sɔ* cannot be the last element in an NP (37h), it cannot be preceded by *soqsɔ* (37i, j), it must always precede the head noun. And it does not allow more than two co-occurring expletives when the head intervenes (37g-j). Let us represent them in sentences as in (38).

(38) a. *Sọ naānj* Àda mà ihe m nà-ème.

Only PN know thing 1sg be-doing

'Ada alone knows what I am doing'

b. *Naānj sọ* Àda mà ihe m nà-ème.

Only PN know thing 1sg be-doing

'Ada alone knows what I am doing'

c. *Sọ* Àda *naānj* mà ihe m nà-ème.

Only PN know thing 1sg be-doing

'Ada alone knows what I am doing'

d. **Naānj* Àda *sọ* mà ihe m nà-ème.

Only PN know thing 1sg be-doing

'Ada alone knows what I am doing'

e. *Naānj sọsọ* Àda mà ihe m nà-ème.

Only PN know thing 1sg be-doing

'Ada alone knows what I am doing'

f. *Sọsọ naānj* Àda mà ihe m nà-ème.

Only PN know thing 1sg be-doing

'Ada alone knows what I am doing'

g. *Naānj* Àda *sọsọ* mà ihe m nà-ème.

Only PN know thing 1sg be-doing

'Ada alone knows what I am doing'

h. *Sọsọ* Àda *naānj* mà ihe m nà-ème.

Only PN know thing 1sg be-doing

'Ada alone knows what I am doing'

What is the motivation for multi-expletive occurrence? The same incremental effect that modifier shift and complement shift have seems to hold here. The combining of more than one expletive in a phrase serves to emphasize, since the meaning is not different with any of them. Before taking a final position, let us examine the combinatorial possibilities of the other three expletives.

4.3.4 EXCEPTIVES WITH OTHER LEXICAL ITEMS

The distribution of expletives with other elements other than nouns shows some interesting behaviour. Apart from *naānj* and *soṣṣo* that depict distributional viability, the other expletives *so*, *alone*, *bèere(so)*, *except*, *tumadi*, *especially*, *obuladi*, *not even*, are as we noted above, pre-modifiers but behave differently when co-occurring with complementizers.

4.3.4.1 EXCEPTIVES - INFINITIVALS

With infinitivals, it is same as with nouns, only *naānj* and *soṣṣo* have different distributions. We see that below.

(39) a. *Naānj* jdi nma ka anyi choro

Only to be good that we want

'We want only goodness'

b. jdi nma *naānj* ka anyi choro

to be good only that we want

'We want only goodness'

(40)a. *Soṣṣo* ikwu eziokwū ka nma

Only to speak true word be better

'Only truthfulness is better...'

b. ikwu eziokwū *soṣṣo* ka nma

to speak truth only be better

'Only truthfulness is better...'

(41) a. *Sọ́ ije òzi ká ọ̀ ná-àgbara ọ̀sọ̀*

Just to run errands that she be running run

'He just avoids running errands'

b. **ije òzi sọ̀*

(42) a. *Bieresọ̀ idē akwụkwọ̀ ọ̀dighị́ ihē ọ̀zọ̀ m chọ̀rọ̀.*

Except to write, book it be-neg thing again I want(rv)

'Except writing, I desire nothing else'

b. **idē akwụkwọ̀ bieresọ̀*

(43) a. *Àda dj umengwụ́ tùmadí isī́ nri.*

PN be laziness especially to cook food

'Ada is lazy especially with cooking'

b. **isī́ nri tùmadí*

(44) a. *Ọ̀bụ́ladí imā́ mmā́ gị́ gá-àzọ̀pụ́ta gị́.*

Not-even to be beauty you will save you

'Not even your beauty will save you'

b. **imā́ mmā́ ọ̀bụ́ladí*

In (39) and (40), *naānị́* and *sọ̀sọ̀*, as expected easily shift within the infinitival domain just as they do for the noun, and in (41) through (44), the other expletives remain pre-modifiers.

4.3.4.2 EXCEPTIVES – COMPLEMENTIZER PLACEMENT

With complementizers, the expletives behave differently from the way they do with nouns and infinitivals as in the data below.

- (45) a. *Naānj* ká ha kwuo eziokwu, anyị alaba.
Only that they say true word, we go
'Only that they say the truth, and then we will go.'
- b. Ká *naānj* ha kwuo eziokwu, anyị alaba.
that only they say true word, we go
'Only that they say the truth, and then we will go.'
- (46) a. *Sọsọ* ná ọ dàrà ùle ká o jì gbue onwe-ya.
Only that 3sg fell exam that 3sg use kill self
'S/he killed her/himself just because s/he failed an examination.'
- b. Ná *sọsọ* ọ dàrà ùle ká o jì gbue onwe-ya.
that only 3sg fell exam that 3sg use kill self
'S/he killed her/himself just because s/he failed an examination.'
- (47) a. *Sọ* ná m sị ya bia ká ọ ná-èwe iwe.
Only that I say him/her come that pron. Be-annoy annoyance
'Only that I asked her/him to come, s/he is annoyed'
- b. Ná *sọ* m sị ya bia ká ọ ná-èwe iwe.
that only I say him/her come that pron. be-annoy annoyance
'Only that I asked her/him to come, s/he is annoyed'
- (48)a. *Bieresọ* ná ha kwuru eziokwu, anyi kaára jìlā.
Except that they say(past) the truth, we would have to go
'Except that they said the truth, we would have gone'

b. Nà *bieresò* ha kwuru eziokwu, anyi kaàra òlù.

Except that they say(past) the truth, we would have to go

'Except that they said the truth, we would have gone'

(49) a. *Tùmàdì* nà ha kwue eziokwu...

Especially that they say(ovs) truth

'Especially, if they say the truth...'

b. Nà *tùmàdì* ha kwue eziokwu

Especially that they say(ovs) truth

'Especially, if they say the truth...'

(50)a. *Òbuladì* mà ha kwue eziokwu ihe e mebiela.

Not even that 3pl say(ovs) truth thing it spoil-perf.

'Even if they say the truth, things have spoilt.'

b. Mà *òbuladì* ha kwue eziokwu ihe e mebiela.

Not even that 3pl say(ovs) truth thing it spoil-perf.

'Even if they say the truth, things have spoilt.'

All the exceptives behave alike when modified with complementizers as we can see in (45) through (51). Even *so* (47) converges both ways. The reason perhaps, could be that the exceptives are adjunct modifiers since they only modify nouns and clauses. Attempts to modify elements other than nouns and clauses fail to converge as in (52) below.

(52) a. * *Naānj* biara ebe a

Only came place this (verb)

b. * *Tumadi* biara ebe a

especially came place this

c. * *Bieresə* nọ ebe à.

Except be place this

(53) a.* *Naānj* niile

Only all (quantifier)

b. * *Tumadi* dum (quantifier)

especially came place this

c. * *Bieresə* ufođu. (quantifier)

'except some'

The expressions modified by exceptives in (52a-c) and (53a-b) are not noun phrases or clauses hence they cannot be modified with the exceptives, but (53c) converges because the quantifier, *ufođu* is seen as a pronominalized with an understood noun. Classifying, we see that the exceptives *naānj*, *sọsọ*, and *sọ* are lexical and clausal modifiers, while the others are clause modifiers only.

4.4 MODIFYING BY REDUPLICATION

Reduplication is an age-old process of word formation which could be partial or complete. It is another strategy of realizing *partitiveness*, *plurality*, *customary activity*, *increase in size*, added *intensity*, and *continuance*. Size, frequency and intensity are features prevalent in shifted modifiers.

4.4.1 ABOUT REDUPLICATION

Reduplication and its attending augmentation involves certain kind of categories as:

i. Common nouns whether concrete or abstract, count or non-count may be duplicated as in (54).

(54)ai. Mmadu mmadu juru ebe ahụ.

Person person fill(rv) place that

'The place overflows with people.'

aii. Mmadu juru ebe ahụ.

Person fill(rv) place that

'There are many people there.'

bi. Q nà-ème nwatà nwatà.	bii. Q nà-ème nwatà.
3sg be doing child child	3sg be doing child
'S/he is very childish.'	'S/he is childish.'
ci. Q nà-ème iwe-iwe.	cii. *Q nà-ème iwe.
3sg be doing anger anger	
S/he behaves angrily'	
di. Q nà-ébe ɔnwụ-ɔnwụ.	*Q nà-ébe ɔnwụ.
3sg be crying death death	
'S/he cries as a dying person'	

In (54a and b) we see that the reduplicated column augments the meaning of the unreduplicated one adding *manyness* as such, reduplication modifies giving adverbial meaning; but in (54c and d) reduplication is both lexical and adverbial in that the unduplicated column fails to converge.

ii. Extreme, definitive or superlative qualities or terms cannot be reduplicated.

See this in (55)

(55)a. *Nke nke	'a particular one'
b. *Ezi ezi	'essence, the best'
c. *ezigbo ezigbo	'essence, the original'

Because the lexical items in (55) denote the last end of the grade scale, quality or measure, they cannot be extended further, hence reduplication fails.

iii. Pure adjectives cannot be reduplicated except as parts of a noun phrase.

(56)a. *oma oma	Ha bụ ndi oma ndi oma
	3pl be people good/fine, people good/fine
	'They are all good/fine people'

- b. **ọcha ọcha* M nwèrè ọkụkọ ọcha ọkụkọ ọcha
 Isg have fowl white fowl white
 'I have mostly white fowls'
- c. **ajọ ajọ* Ajọ ihe ajọ ihená-ème n'òbòdò
 Evil thing evil thing be doing in village
 'A lot of evil things happen in the village.'

In the examples in (56), we see that the adjectives cannot be reduplicated. In fact, it is the nouns that are reduplicated in all the examples above.

iv. Agentives, infinitivals and gerunds can be reduplicated. The structure of the reduplicated agentives vary according to their verb forms whether simple, compound, or complex verbs. Simple and complex verb agentives obligatorily retain their complements, while compound verb agentives optionally delete their complements. We can see this in (57).

- (57)a. *Èkwu eme èkwu eme*
 sayer doer, sayer doer
 'people who keep their words'
- b. *Ògbu agụ ogbu agụ*
 killer lion killer lion
 'lion killers'
- c. *Òrigbu origbu*
 cheat cheat
 'people who cheat others'
- d. *Òri n'ìkè ori n'ìkè*
 cater by power
 'people who live by extortion'

The examples in (57a and b), are simple verb agentives and have their complements intact, so also the complex agentives (57d) but the compound (57c) may retain or lose their complements. The infinitival and gerunds are reduplicated as in (58a, b) and (58c, d) respectively.

- (58)a. Óbòdo niile nọ n'iri-ji iri-ji n'owa Qgọst.
 Country all be in to eat yam to eat yam in month August.
 'All villages are all in new yam festival in August.'
- b. Ije ozi ije ozi ka Ada mere taa
 to go errand to go errand that Ada did today
 'All that Ada did today was to run errands'
- c. Òriri oriri kà ha chorọ.
 feasting feasting that they want
 'All they want is feasting'
- d. Ada mèrè ha niile ọzụzụ ọzụzụ
 Ada do(rv) them all buying buying
 'Ada went on a buying spree.'

From the data in (58) we see that the infinitivals and gerunds can also undergo reduplication still giving a meaning of frequency and measure. Note the tonal change in the reduplicated gerunds, the first syllable of the second member changes from Low to High.

v. Quantifiers can be duplicated for intensive purposes. Quantifiers exhibit features not in the other lexical items. They can be reduplicated only when post-modifying a noun but fail when shifted.

- (59)a. Mmadu ụfọdụ ụfọdụ no ebe a. * ụfọdụ ụfọdụ mmadu
 Person some some be place this
 'Very few people are here'
- b. Mmadu ọtụtụ ọtụtụ no ebe a. * ọtụtụ ọtụtụ mmadu
 Person many many be place this
 'So many people are here'
- c. Mmadu ọbụlà ọbụlà ekwukwala okwu
 person any any talk not talk
 'Nobody at all should say anything'
- d. Mmadu niile nile riri nri
 Person all all eat(rv) food
 'Every single person ate the food'

Note from the examples in (59) that the quantifiers double their effect when duplicated, *some* becomes *very few* (59a), *many* becomes *so many* (59b) any becomes *none at all* (59c) and *all*, becomes *to the last person, without exception* (59d). Reduplication in these instances intensifies.

vi. The heads can be omitted in an intensive reduplication but a non-head element cannot be omitted as is the case in the reduplicated quantifiers in (59). In all the cases the noun head can be repeated as in *mmadu niile mmadu niile*(59d), same goes for the others.

vii. Numerals can all be reduplicated since they can easily serve as nouns; however they give a partitive reading as shown in (60).

- (60) a. Otù otù 'one each'
 b. Abụọ abụọ 'two each / in twos'

- c. Atọ atọ 'three each / in threes'
- d. Ise ise 'five each / in fives'
- e. Àsatọ àsatọ 'eight each / in eights'

All the numerals in (60) give partitive readings and cannot be otherwise since they are definitive.

viii. Prepositional phrases are easy reduplicates. Prepositional phrases most times are adverbial adjuncts hence the examples (61) all have adverbial readings.

- (61)a. N'otù n'otù
by one by one
'one by one /in sequence'
- b. N'iwe n'iwe
in anger in anger
'furiously'
- c. N'ike n'ike
with might with might
'in great haste/hastily'
- d. N'isi n'isi
in head in head
'head to head, according to rank'
- e. Nà mby na mby
at beginning at beginning
'at the very beginning'

They give a sequential, manner or whatever necessary adverbial readings in context. Note that (61b, and c) translate as English adverbs while (61e) implies an intensive reading.

ix. Noun Adverbials can also be duplicated as in (62).

- | | |
|--|---|
| <p>(62)a. Bia ugbu à ugbu à
Come now this this now
'Come right now'</p> <p>b. àchoghj m ya moolj moolj.
agr-want-neg 1sg it at all at all
'I don't want it at all.'</p> <p>c. Ñua ogwụ kwụbọchj kwụbọchj.
Drink medicine each day each day
'Take the medicine daily'</p> | <p>(63)a. Bia ugbu à.
Come now this
'Come now'</p> <p>b. àchoghj m ya moolj.
agr-want-neg 1sg it at all
'I don't want it at all.'</p> <p>c. Ñua ogwụ kwụbọchj.
Drink medicine each day
'Take the medicine daily.'</p> |
|--|---|

The adverbial *ugbu à* in (62) *intensifies* giving a different reading from (63) because of reduplication. On the other hand, the other two adverbials in (62b and c) show no visible change in meaning when reduplicated, except that of *emphasis*. This goes to prove that duplication can be used for various functional purposes.

x. Nominal Adverbs can also be reduplicated as in (62). The nominal adverbs generally function as adverbs would in English. When reduplicated, they are mostly intensified.

- | | |
|--|--|
| <p>(64)a. O nà-eme nwaayoo nwaayoo.
3sg be doing slowness slowness
'S/he acts very slowly'</p> | <p>(65)a. O nà-eme nwaayoo.
3sg be doing slowness
'S/he acts slowly'</p> |
|--|--|

- | | |
|---------------------------------|-----------------------|
| b. Q ná-ème ofuma ofuma. | b. Q ná-ème ofuma. |
| 3sg be doing well well | 3sg be doing well |
| 'S/he is doing very well.' | 'S/he is doing well.' |
| c. Mée ngwa ngwa ngwa ngwa | c. Mée ngwa. |
| Do(ovs) quick quick quick quick | Do(ovs)quick |
| 'Be very, very quick.' | 'Be quick.' |

The incremental meaning of (64) versus (65) comes from reduplicating words that already have adverb features.

4.4.2 CONCLUSION

Having seen the possible effects of full reduplication, it would be germane to aver that reduplication is an overt outworking of a rather covert feature that may indicate distribution, plurality, customary activity, and increase in size, added intensity, and continuance (*a la* Sapir 1921). Reduplication can be lexical (54c, d) and can indicate size, frequency and intensity. We conclude that reduplication and modifier-shift are geared towards the same goal in the Igbo computational system.

4.5 CONJUNCTION

A conjunction is a part of speech that joins words, phrases, and clauses and indicates a relationship between the conjoined elements. Conjunction was adequately covered in Chomsky's earlier works like *Aspects* which has a transformation known as Teonj. However, because of the need for structural symmetry, the subsequent Generative Grammars ignored it because it could not fit into the theory's evolving configurational concept. One such concept is the *binarity* principle which says:

(66) All nonterminal nodes are binary-branching. (Radford 1997:98)

According to Radford, (66) claims that all nonterminal nodes branch into two and only two immediate constituents, never more than two. Representing a binary branching conjunction phrase has not been feasible in Generative grammar. The X-bar syntax, Minimalist Program or even the improved Derivation by phase which makes use of repeated merger operations has no answer as to how to present a binary merged structure of the conjoined elements as in (67)

And also (67) violates the Uniformity Principle. It is difficult to say which of the constituents in (67) projects. Certainly, (67) does not comply with the binary branching phrase structure format. As a result, it would be erroneously termed ill-formed using Minimalist or X-bar architecture. Yet we all know that it is well-formed and acceptable not only in Igbo but virtually cross-linguistically. However, considering the fact that other functional items like the complementizers, agreement, aspect, inflection, agreement, and tense are considered as functional heads, in the Minimalist Program; what stops conjunction from also heading the Conjunction Phrase – ConjP. If we take the double conjunction cases like *ma Obi ma Ada*, *both Obi and Ada*, as the norm, then, we can have a seeming binary configuration as in (68).

(68)a.

NP conjunction

(68)b.

IP conjunction

(68) c.

CP conjunction

What (68) implies is that the conjunction phrase directly dominates two copies of itself depending on whether what are conjoined are noun phrases, clauses or subordinate clauses. Following, empty category principle, conjunction phrases with only one conjunction in the middle would assume the *conj_i* to be empty as in (69a, b).

(69)a.

(69)b. Obi nà Àda siri nri rie.

PN conj. PN cook(past) food eat(past)

'Obi and Ada cooked some food and ate'

However, the Conj. phrase schema as I have presented here may run into problems the moment we have more than two conjoints, for then there would be need for a ternary branching nonterminal node as in (70a and b).

(70)a. Obi nà Àda nà Chike bjàrà ebe à.

PN conj. PN conj PN come(rv) place this

'Obi, Ada and Chike came here.'

(70) b.

One way (70b) could be remedied is to stipulate that Conjunction phrase is free to have non-binary nodes having the following implications: a) it will be an exception to the general binary node; b) It will add complexity which MP tries to avoid through minimal structures. Another way is to assume that the conjunction is in the governing category of a noun such that all the conjunction can be under a noun phrase. This is true to the extent that in a noun phrase like that in (70a), we have the three conjoints as subjects of the sentence. But this also cannot suffice for there are practically three sentences with three subjects in (70a). Again considering that conjunction is recursive like all other structures in grammatical operations, it cannot be equated with complementizers, or wh-elements which subordinate the following elements of same kind as in (71).

(71) *Ónye kà Ada gwara nà onye siri nri ahụ gbàrà ọsọ mgbè m hụrụ nà ọ dj njo?*

Wh comp Ada tell(rv) comp wh cook(rv) food that run(rv) run wh 1sg see(rv) comp...

"Who did Ada tell that the person who cooked that food ran away when I saw that it was bad?"

In (71), we see that there are three wh-elements, three complementizers and the sentence can be symmetrically represented in a phrase structure because of subordination. But in the case of conjunction, no subordination is involved since conjunction joins equal terms. It follows that positing a multi-branching or ternary node for conjunction would be the most logical thing to do. To this end, we propose that the conjunction phrase is an exception to the binary structures where Conj serves as the head of the ConjP.

4.6 THEME-GOAL SWITCH IN DOUBLE OBJECT STRUCTURES

Accounting for the double object construction has proved very difficult to explain for scholars in the generative model. This may stem from the assumption that constituent structures of phrases and sentences are built only in a binary-branching hierarchical structure. Chomsky (1984) in accounting for the ditransitive objects of the verb says;

The primary object of a transitive verb is its only object but the primary object of a ditransitive verb is the one nearest to it. (Chomsky 1984:94)

What this implies is that the first object, otherwise called O1(Object 1), receives case from the verb in the usual way on the assumption that case is assigned to the adjacent phrase (O1) and that the second object, otherwise called O2 (Object 2), receives secondary case or thematic role from the same verb. This presupposes that O1 will always have primary case though not the same

thematic role while O2 takes on the secondary case. The issue is not clear-cut with the Igbo data before us. There are instances of shift in positions between O1 and O2 whenever *theme* is an understood pronominal item and the verb cannot be said to particularly assign primary case or role to its nearest object.

(72) Qbi nyere Ada ego.
Source give goal theme
'Obi gave Ada some money'

(73) Qbi nyere yà Ada.
Source give theme goal
'Obi gave some money to Ada'

Note that *goal* comes before *theme* in (72) but *theme* comes before *goal* in (73) where *theme* is a pronominal. This would be discussed in section 4.6.3. Meanwhile, Let us do an overview of the double object structures in Igbo.

4.6.1 DOUBLE OBJECTS IN IGBO

The Igbo ditransitive verbs can be grouped into two: those having extensional applicative morphemes and those with zero extension.

4.6.1.1 EXTENSIONAL APPLICATIVE DITRANSITIVES

Virtually every transitive verb in the language can be accommodated in this group by way of adding the applicative morpheme to show the recipient, benefactive or affected participant. Some of the verbs include:

- zutà-ā-rà buy in-appl.-past 'buy for'
- chotà-ā-rà find-appl.-past 'found for'
- wètà-ā-rà bring-appl.-past 'brought for'
- rità-ā-rà gain-appl.-past 'gained for'

• si-ĩ-rì cook-appl.-past 'cooked for'

• bùtè-ē-rè buy-appl.-past 'brought for'

(74) Ada zutáārà Ebō olà.

Ada buy in-appl.-past Ebo a ring

Source goal theme

'Ada bought Ebō a ring or Ada bought a ring for Ebo.'

(75) Ada chotáārà Ebō ulo obibi

Ada find-appl.-past Ebo house residence

Source goal theme

'Ada found Ebo a residential house or found a residential house for Ebo.'

(76) Ada wètáārà Ebō mkpuru osisi

Ada bring-appl.-past Ebo fruits of tree

Source goal theme

'Ada brought Ebo some fruits or brought some fruits for Ebo.'

Without the extentional *-rā-*, *-rī-*, or *-rē-* (depending on vowel harmony) morpheme, (realized as *ā*, *ī*, or *ē*, through a phonological process of deletion of adjacent occurring identical morpheme) the verbs ordinarily are monotransitive and the addition of the morpheme makes the verb capable of subcategorizing double objects.

The order of arrangement of the verb internal arguments is that *Goal* occurs nearest to the verb than the *Theme* (Grimshaw 1994). This is the case in (74) through (76). In (74) *Ebō* is the *Goal* or recipient participant while *olà* is the *Theme* of the verb *izutā* - to buy. The same process obtains in (75) and (76).

4.6.1.2 ZERO EXTENSION DITRANSITIVE

These are verbs that are inherently ditransitive in the environment that they occur. They require no extensional morpheme to make them ditransitive. They include:

- *inyē* 'to give'
- *imē* 'to make'
- *ikpọ* 'to call'

They are exemplified as in (77).

(77) *Ada nyere Obi akwukwọ.*

Ada give (past) Obi book

'Ada gave Obi a book'

(78) *Ndị ichiè mèrè Obi Ezè.*

People elder make(past) Obi king

'The elders made Obi a king'

(79) *Anyị kpọrọ ụmụ nwoke ahụ ndị ohi*

We call (past) offsprings man that people thief

'We called those men thieves' or 'we took those men for thieves.'

The examples (77) through (79) do not require a *-ta* applicative morpheme to make them capable of subcategorizing double objects. Apart from not having extensional morphemes, they are not different, syntactically or semantically, from the ones with extensional morphemes. They are typical cases of ditransitive verbs. When the two objects are lexical NPs the order of occurrence is that Goal precedes Theme, however, when Theme is a pronominal, it precedes Goal. This same order obtains for the extensional ones.

4.6.2 PRONOMINAL THEME/GOAL SHIFT

As noted above, the canonical order of objects arrangement is for goal to come before theme; but it is found that theme comes before goal when theme is a pronominal as in (80) through (83).

- (80) Ada nyèrè yà Obi.
Ada give (past) it (pron. Theme) Obi(Goal)
'Ada gave it to Obi'
- (81) Ndí ichie mèèrè yà Obi.
People elder did it (theme) Obi (goal)
'The elders did it for Obi...'
- (82) Anyi kpọrọ ha ndị ohi.
We call (past) them people thief
'We called them thieves'
- (83) Anyi wèrè ha ndị ohi
We take (past) them people thief
'We took them for thieves'

(80) through (82) show shades of pronominal placements in the Igbo double object structures. In (80), *Theme* precedes *Goal* since it is a pronoun. (83) has an implicative reading which could follow from (78) that *Obi* was made a king. Without such implicative reading, (83) would be ambiguous since the pronoun has an external reference. Although (82) and (83) are grammatical, they give readings completely different from (80) and as such, we can safely assume that they are different lexical items. They represent a different class of ditransitives, in that, they are better classified as small clauses; the two objects are of equal

status, for one can be assumed to be in apposition to the other. Where goal precedes a pronominal theme, the result is illicit as in (84) through (87).

(84) Ada nyèrè *Obi yà.

PN Source give (past) PN (goal) it (pron. theme)

(85) *Anyi nyèrè yà ya.

(86) *Anyi kpòrò ndi ohi ha.

(87) *Anyi wèrè ndi ohi ha.

(84) and (87) fail to converge notwithstanding that *theme* occurs before *goal*.

(84) fails because the pronominal *theme* must come before *goal*. (85), on the other hand, fails because of the co-occurrence of two pronominals not bound within the clause. Also the pronoun *ha* in (86) and (87) is not a *theme* object, since it retains its high tone. As mentioned above, the pronoun *ha* is a co-complement which constitutes a small clause. The structural possibilities between the two objects of the transitive verb can be as in (88).

(88) a. Ada nyèrè Obi egò.	Lexical Goal and Lexical Theme
b. *Ada nyèrè egò ya.	Lexical Theme and Pronominal Goal
c. Ada nyèrè ya egò.	Pronominal Goal and Lexical Theme
d. *Ada nyèrè yà ya	Pronominal Theme and Pronominal Goal
e. Ada nyèrè ya Obi.	Pronominal Theme and Lexical Goal
f. *Ada nyèrè Obi ya.	Lexical Goal and pronominal Theme

Of the six possible collocations of the double objects given in (88), a, c, and e, are convergent while the rest are not. What then are responsible for the variation in occurrences? Reasons have been advanced to explain just the pronominal theme/lexical goal collocation; though syntactically motivated.

Scholars, among whom are Baedekar (1986), Saah and Eze (1997), and Radford (1997) suggest that the pronominal theme precedence is an instance of cliticization.

Baedekar holds that the verb attracts the pronominal clitic to itself. Saah and Eze reject verb attraction on the grounds that it lacks conceptual explanation but opt for an empty XP projection in which Goal is the Specifier of X and Theme is the Complement of X. The empty X node houses a pronominal clitic which surfaces when theme is a pronominal. The schema for this is drawn in (89).

The schema in (89) is explained such that the pronominal *Theme* is base-generated in AGRO head as a clitic and that the AGRO head always has a covert pronominal clitic *theme* which becomes visible whenever *theme* is a pronominal. The question then is; why does the pronominal theme move to the higher position above goal after cliticizing with the empty X node?

Radford (1997) sees clitics as products of adjacent constituents merger phonologically conditioned. If that is the environment for clitics, then the pronominal theme would have to cliticize with the empty category X and may not move. We reject that analysis on the grounds of not having convincing evidence.

Dealing generally with the double object construction, Hale and Keyser (1996) suggest possible configurations which assume the same constraints applicable to lexical argument structures. The structures are represented here in (90).

(90c) without doubt is similar to Saah and Eze's (1977) XP schema and (90a) is the normal head/modifier or head/complement relation (cf. Emenanjo, 1978). (90b) does not apply to this study. The problem with assuming the same constraints that applies to verb argument structure with double object construction as posited by Hale and Keyser is that objects do not assign any case or thematic role. They only require linearly adjacent co-objects and not arguments. An alternative analysis is explored below.

4.6.3 FURTHER ON PRONOMINAL THEME-GOAL SHIFT

If we assume that the two adjacent objects of a ditransitive verb are in the computation taken to constitute a phrase, say XP (Saah and Eze (1997)), then the realization for the phrase may either be a projection of *Goal* or a projection of *Theme*. That oversimplifies the issue and does not give a correct reflection of the problem. If we consider the co-occurrence possibilities of the double object,

as shown in (88), represented here as (91), one notices that the issue is more of a semantic selection than syntactic.

- (91) a. Ada nyèrè Obi egō. Lexical **Goal** and Lexical **Theme**
 Source give goal theme
 'Ada gave Obi some money.'
- b. *Ada nyèrè egō ya. Lexical **Theme** and Pronominal **Goal**
 Source give theme goal
- c. Ada nyèrè ya egō. Pronominal **Goal** and Lexical **Theme**
 Source give goal theme
 'Ada gave him some money.'
- d. *Ada nyèrè yà ya Pronominal **Theme** and Pronominal **Goal**
 Source give theme goal
- e. Ada nyèrè ya Obi. Pronominal **Theme** and Lexical **Goal**
 Source give theme goal
 'Ada gave him some money.'
- f. *Ada nyèrè Obi ya. Lexical **Goal** and pronominal **Theme**
 Source give goal theme

It is obvious that *Obi* in (91a) is the recipient, while *egō* is what was received. (91b) crashes because; *egō* can never be the recipient. (91c) is acceptable because, the pronoun is understood to refer to an external recipient. (91d) fails because two pronouns occurring as objects of a verb cannot both receive case from the same verb thereby making the statement ambiguous. (91e) converges since the pronominal refers to theme. Note that (91c and d) both have

pronominals with different readings. One refers to a human recipient not mentioned in the sentence, while the other refers to an item that was received. This state of things is brought about by the fact that the 3rd person pronoun in Igbo has two readings. One is 'plus human' and the other is 'minus human'. The only way to determine which pronoun is in use is for one of the objects to be a noun.

However, (91f) shows that under no situation should a lexical *Goal* precede a pronominal *Theme*. Thus, where one of the objects is a pronominal, the pronominal must come first then the lexical one. Also Ndimele, (personal communication) holds that the pronoun is attracted to the verb in order to receive case. That is why it must come before the lexical one. Again the pronoun occurring after the noun would have a reading as a modifier of the noun and not as Theme as shown in (91f). One general structural rule derivable from this analysis is this:

- (92) Pronominal first rule: A double object pronominal must precede its lexical one in order to have case assigned by the verb.

This rule seems a more economic way of explaining the syntax of double objects in Igbo and languages like it since it proposes a simpler and easier way for a child learning the language. Simply put, where there is a pronominal in double objects, put the pronominal first. Given minimalist assumptions; that where there are two possible configurations for a given operation, the one involving the least effort should be preferred over the less economic one, it follows that (92) should be preferred over Chomsky's (1984) O1 and O2 case-theoretic analysis and Saah's AGRO clitic analysis.

4.7 SUMMARY

In this chapter, we have we have looked at other forms of modifier shifts; specifically, using the *imā* verb complements, the subject/complement shift, duplication, modification by conjunction, and the Goal/theme shift. Just as some noun modifiers permit shifting to show features of intensity, measure, size, etc., so does the *imā* verb and the subject/object which should be object/object, shift. Also ditransitive verbs permit the switching of the sequences of its thematic roles when one of the roles is filled by a pronominal. This shift is conditioned by the verb and possibly because of the need for pronouns to be nearer to case assigners, the verb being the only one in these environments.

CHAPTER FIVE

SUMMARY AND CONCLUSIONS

5.1 SUMMARY

Modifier shift, as we have observed in this study, is not a redundant phenomenon in Igbo syntax. It is used among other things to add features such as intensity, size, measure, continuance and grade. This, we see in the noun modifier-head shift, duplication. The *ima* skill verb inherently permits shift of complements within its domain. Also we see that subject/complement shift is driven possibly by edge feature; we also posited a revisit of the conjunction phrase, adding that it might well be better to recognize it as the only non-binary branching node, since its exclusion from the structural scheme of things leaves us with an incomplete grammar of languages.

Given the features identified, modifier shift becomes a syntactic process that is sensitive to the syntax and semantics of the particular constituents that shift, else other forms could have been amenable to it. It makes no real difference whether we are dealing with shifting occurring within a noun phrase domain or that within a clause-like segment as in Chapter Four. The point is that other forms of shift analyzed, such as; subject/complement shift, the *ima* verb complement, and the pronominal *theme* precedence of the double object structure are all movements within a domain. In a way, modifier-shift is domain specific and serves to add certain nuances that are not possible in their base positions. To this regard, we hold that it is feature-driven.

Given that modifier-shift is feature-driven and domain specific, it follows that this analysis fits perfectly into the Greed theoretic Minimalist architecture which locates syntactic operations to given structural domains. In addition, we hold that the obligatory shifts are motivated by Greed and ESI while the optional shifts are motivated by ESI alone. That is, the obligatory modifier shifts like that involving *ezi*, the essence, best, *ezigbo*, original, and *oke*, high, do so because Greed requires that they shift or move to initial position since they are inherently of the extreme grade, but ESI allows the move for altruistic purposes. The optional cases are simply to obtain features of grade not evident in situ.

5.2 CONTRIBUTIONS

The thesis upholds major tenets of the Minimalist Program but also modified some in order to adequately analyse Igbo modifier-head shifts. It upholds the Minimalist Program in asserting that shifting is feature-driven; however, it makes a departure from the Minimalist Program permitting both the D and the N as heads though with different functions.

This is completely conforms with the uniqueness condition in that D and N are heads not of the same items. By positing that the leftmost constituent of the phrases are heads while all other satellites are modifiers, we maintain a fairly simple, learnable structure for the computational system. Even modifiers convert to heads when in initial positions. A second departure is the fact that head-to-head movement is not strictly followed in the cases of shifting since the shift occurs within the same governing category, N, V as the case may be. A third departure is the non-binary branching proposition for the conjoined structures.

It has also demonstrated that modifier-shift is a possible syntactic process in Igbo although it has not been given significant consideration by scholars.

Finally, the thesis advocates the recognition of the place of the Conjunction category as the only non-binary-branching non-terminal node in the Minimalist Program. The advantage of this is that there would be a complete account of all the lexical items in languages.

5.3 CONCLUSIONS

The central concern of this work has been on showing that modifier-head shift constitutes a peculiar kind of displacement in language that has not been given attention by Igbo scholars. Other major conclusions in this work include:

1. We consider modifier-shifting to be feature-driven within a modified tenets of the Minimalist Program and that the moved element becomes the head following a head first parameter for all noun phrases.
2. The features, measure, intensity, grade, and continuance, can be obtained through modifier shift or through reduplication.
3. If movements are operations that occur in a given phase, e.g., VP and IP, (Chomsky 1999), then NPs should be recognised as phases since the same operations noticed in VPs and IPs are evident in the noun phrases.
4. The Igbo nominal phrase structure obeys the binary parameter selection of UG maintaining a modifier-last position, where pre-modifiers are evidence of modifier shift which converts the modifiers to heads.
5. Shifts like the subject/complement shift are purely ESI-driven since they are optional.

6. The subject/object switching phenomenon in Igbo is a case of two kinds of objects swapping places.
7. Given that the parametric variation is a matter of morphology and the word order of a particular language is due to the strength of the features of the functional categories (Chomsky, 1994:167), the question of the exact positions heads and modifiers occupy in the syntax of given languages becomes easy to determine.

5.4 UNRESOLVED PROBLEMS

Certainly, there is no theory that can explain all the processes in language without having issues that it cannot handle. In spite of all the claims we made in this work, a number of issues still remain unresolved.

Determining the node into which the shifted element moves remains unresolved as the modified theory used in this study cannot account for that.

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